

**PSYCHOMETRIC EVALUATION OF 2018 WAEC AND NECO
MATHEMATICS OBJECTIVE TEST ITEMS: EVIDENCE FROM CROSS
RIVER STATE, NIGERIA**

BY

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**DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATIONAL FOUNDATIONS
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**IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD
OF DOCTORATE DEGREE (Ph.D) IN EDUCATIONAL MEASUREMENT AND
EVALUATION.**

DECEMBER, 2019

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this dissertation on “Assessment of dimensionality, local independence and differential item functioning of 2018 mathematics WAEC and NECO objective test items in Cross River State, Nigeria” is an original work written by me. It is a record of my research work and has not been presented before in any previous publication.

OWOR, EFFIOM OWOR**Signature.....****Reg. No.: EDT/Ph.D/16/003****Date:.....****CERTIFICATION**

We certified that this thesis entitle “Psychometric Evaluation of 2018 WAEC and NECO Mathematics Objective Test Items: Evidence from Cross River State, Nigeria” by Owor, Effiom Owor (Reg. No.: EDT/Ph.D/16/003), carried out under our supervision, has been examined and found to have met the regulations of the University of Calabar. We therefore recommend the work for the award of Doctorate Degree (Ph.D) in Educational Measurement and Evaluation.

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the psychometric properties of the 2018 Mathematics objective test items administered by the West African Examinations Council (WAEC) and the National Examinations Council (NECO) in Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, the research assessed the dimensionality, local independence, and differential item functioning (DIF) of the test items using Item Response Theory (IRT) models. A quantitative research design was adopted, utilizing secondary data obtained from students' responses. Statistical analyses were conducted to determine whether the test items satisfied the assumptions of unidimensionality and local independence, and to identify items exhibiting DIF across relevant subgroups. The findings revealed that while a majority of the items met the assumptions of dimensionality and local independence, a number of items demonstrated significant DIF, indicating potential bias. The study concludes that although the examinations are generally reliable, some items may compromise fairness and validity. It is recommended that test developers conduct routine psychometric evaluations to improve the quality and equity of standardized assessments in Nigeria.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background to the study

Education is considered the world over as the fundamental wheel on which personal and societal success revolved. It has been recognized as the gadget for acquiring knowledge and experiences with which sustainable development is attained in any society. One of the major objectives of education ideally is to help the students earn their living and to make them independent. This objective could be achieved by offering mathematics in school which is regarded as one of the most important subjects in the school curriculum. This subject is significance to contemporary society because it provides vital foundation on the knowledge of any particular economy. The subject is indispensable in every fields of endeavour. Mathematics forms the root of the largest part of scientific and industrial research and development as many complex systems and structures in the contemporary society can only be understood using mathematical concepts. Also, much of the blueprint and control of high-technological systems depends largely on mathematical inputs and outputs which ultimately lead to national development.

The tool of mathematics in the development of any society lies in the principle of measurement (Carroll, 2012). Measurement according to Baghaei (2010) is seen as the procedure for obtaining a mathematical explanation of the extent to which a person or object possesses a particular trait. Measurement, beyond its general definition, refers to the set of measures and the principles on how to use the measures in educational tests and appraisal. Some of the fundamental ideologies of measurement in educational assessment

would be raw scores, derived scores, standard scores, etc which is strictly indirect. It is the analysis of data such as scores obtained from educational assessments to surmise the proficiencies and abilities of learners with the main focus on whether such tests are reliable and valid.

This inference of student's abilities can be achieved by the administration of a test. By definition, a test is a tool that calls for learners to complete a cognitive obligation by reacting to a standard set of questions or task. It is intended to appraise an examinee's knowledge, proficiency, skills and so on in many other topics in a particular subject matter. This test could be administered formally or informally by a classroom teacher or examination bodies such as the West African Examination Council (WAEC) and the National Examination Council (NECO). The main thrust of these bodies and their experts center on ways of providing worthwhile test items to the test takers in a cost-effective and conducive examination atmosphere as well as compare tests that meet both the rationale and provision articulated by psychometricians and the procedural standards for quality test items. Chen and Wang (2007) noted that the primary challenge of any examination body is its duty to produce a well calibrated instrument that is sensitive to the indicators of the psychological qualities which make up the objectives to be measured.

Psychological measurement, experts say transcends beyond mere administration of test to test takers and awarding of marks. It is the duties of the examination bodies and their personnel to provide provisional explanatory propositions concerning the test scores to facilitate their interpretations (Lee, 2004). This interpretation of the test scores has been carried out under the auspices of classical test theory over five decades ago. This global and or traditional test scores in judging student's performance have been argued by test

experts as being rather shady and capable of muffling the finer details of the individual items in a test. In a bid to resolve this controversy, the Item Response Theory (IRT) has been developed to overcome its shortcoming.

It is disheartening to observe that given the quality of these examination bodies and the qualification of personnel, the development and administration of test items, student's performances on these test items in our primary and post primary institutions as observed are still based on the global scores a test taker obtains in judging his true ability thereby neglecting the set of items a construct represents, the dimensions of such items as well as how informative the responses to the items provide.

Teachers nowadays as observed are not interested in determining what constructs a subset of item responses reflect, thus, it is not comprehensible how to merge those responses into a lone test-let score. When a set of items are locally dependent, it is expected that the items are bundled into polytomous super-items. Teachers in our school system as observed are unable to construct items which can partial out set of items that are linked to a common trait which form one polytomous items in order to establish the power of local item dependence in the middle of items within each super-item. Non determination of subset of items representing a particular construct can blow up the reliability and give a false idea of the accuracy and value of the test.

Chen and Thissen (2000) noted that the infringement of the local independence postulation can have significant effects on test parameter estimation and on ability estimates, stressing that provisional prospect of attaining any pattern of scores on independent items is the result of the prospect for the separate items. It is consequently, important to guarantee the precision of the discrimination parameters, given that it serves

as a manifestation of the item quality and the test quality. None determination of a local independence of items in a particular test can strongly create bias in the variance estimate of students' ability (Chen & Thissen, 2011) and produce biased ability estimates.

Bujan (2015) acknowledged a number of possible causes of violation of local independence. A number of them are independent of the item's content: external support, such as assistance from a teacher, fatigue, item or response format, speediness (if students do not get to item j , they will definitely not accomplish item $j+1$), the gender of the students, they type of school attended, school location etc.

It is argued that if the local independence postulation does not hold in a test, then the validity of the test cannot be ascertained. If the consequence of local independence is significant, it is complex to say what dimension the test is. Even if the consequence is little, the derived scores will be polluted. Violation of local independence in a test would results in the overestimation of reliability and consequently leading to falsely little standard errors of estimates. This could be a very stern hitch in computerized adaptive testing where normal error of estimates is the decisive factor for stopping the test (Baghaei, 2012).

Dependency in the middle of items can blow up reliability and provide a fake notion of the accuracy and value of the test. It is regrettable to observe that some test constructed violates local independence assumption in that if a test taker fails to respond to a certain item rightly the response may impact the other responses on the next item which can ultimately affect the result of the test taker on the entire test.

If items in a test are constructed on grounds of local independence and arranged in ascending order of difficulty, it is expected that a test taker will respond correctly to test items until a position when his/her ability diminishes. On the other hand, unidimensionality

implies that test takers and items can be described by a single ability measuring a particular construct. This assumption is met when a set of items comprising a particular construct measures the same underlying ability and test takers use only this ability to answer to the test items making such a construct (Reckase & McKinley, 2009).

Tests constructed in education and other fields are generally anticipated to measure more or less of some constructs. Many of these tests constructed to measure a single variable are nonetheless designed to measure diverse aspects of the variable. These tests are often composed of subscales which measure these various aspects. These different aspects are conceptually related to the variable and are in use because they make the scale more valid than if only one of the aspects were measured. The items in these tests are expected to unlikely to be perfectly correlated to the degree that the test items are not perfectly correlated, to the degree that the test could be considered to measure a unidimensional construct.

Reckase (2013) noted that a multidimensional test somehow contaminates the test. When subtest items which measure these items are included in a test, the construct measured is more complex than if only one subtest was used. Measurements of the complex construct using subtest items can be seen to increase its validity further than that which would be achieved if only one aspect were measured using only one subtest. When a set of items are locally dependent, they are usually packaged into polytomous super-items, that is, the set of items which are linked to a familiar stimulus are regarded as as one polytomous item to partial out the power of local item dependence among items inside each super-item.

It is regrettable to observe that teachers, examiners and indeed some examination bodies do not check test items to ascertain if indeed they add to the quality of measurement,

or if the items are capable of differentiating the abilities of male and female students, if the item are capable of differentiating the proficiencies of students who attend schools in the town areas and those from the rural areas or if the items are capable of differentiating the abilities of students who attend private schools and their colleagues from government, or if the items do not have any technical problems such as more than one right answer in a multiple choice item or if there are consistent items measuring a particular construct.

The goal of this research is to investigate the effect of violations of dimensionality and local independence of 2018 mathematics objectives tests of WAEC and NECO as well as its effects on test takers proficiency and response pattern to test items.

1.2. Theoretical framework

Two theories guided the study. The theories are:

Classical Test Theory (CTT)

Item Response Theory (IRT)

Classical Test Theory (CTT)

Classical test theory is the theory that forecasts the outcome of psychological testing such as the difficulty of the item and the ability of students. The theory was propounded by Charles Spearman in (1904) in his article of test theory which made up of true and error scores, though his work was first introduced by George Udney Yule in 1936. This theory has been the brain behind most educational measurement associated with the construction, administration and analysis of achievement tests and other related psychometric processes. It is a body of interrelated psychometric theory that is essentially concerned with the evaluation of the global scores test takers obtained in a given test.

Measurement experts engaged in testing without the basic test tools required to establish the true test taker's abilities, hence ending up in data analysis with haphazard operations.

Classical test theory has the following tools which are regarded as the main features of determining test taker's indices, these features include:

- a. P-value: this refers to the proportion of test takers selecting an item correct over the overall students who took the test. That is, the relative ease of a particular test item. It is also called item difficulty.
- b. d-value: this refers to the point bi-serial correlation between the item alternatives and the test. That is, ability of the test items to be shared among students who know and those who do not know the answer. It is usually divided into three sections, high ability, average and low ability students. It is also called item discrimination.
- c. Mean of test takers, that is the number right scores of the test takers.
- d. Standard deviation of the test takers' scores
- e. Skewness and kurtosis of test takers' scores.
- f. Reliability of the test, that is usually the Kuder Richardson formula 20 (KR-20)

The primary motive of the classical test theory in educational and psychological measurement is the proposition of the test takers in a test which is denoted by relationship linking the observed score (X), True score (T) and the Error score (E) in the students. It is assumed that an observed score is a combination of true score plus some error.

This can be put mathematically as:

$$X_o = X \pm X_e$$

Where:

X_o = the Observed score

X = the True score

X_e = the Error score

The observed score (X_o) is the one given to the test takers based on their responses to the test items; the true score (X) is the true performances of the test takers while the error score (E) is regarded as that which occurs as a result of our being humans who are prone to mistakes during measurement processes. Nevertheless, the above equation posits that a student observed score in a test involves some amount of error which may be working to his advantages or disadvantages. When the error in a test works to the advantage of the test taker, his test score will be inflated by that error score. Similarly, when the error score works to the disadvantage of the test taker, his test score will be depleted by that error score. This inflation and depletion of the test taker's score signifies the \pm in the above equation.

The importance of this theory to the current research cannot be overemphasized as the theory provides parameters such as reliability, discrimination and factor loadings depending on the sample being used.

Item Response Theory (IRT)

Item Response Theory (IRT) is a theory of testing based on the association between testees' performance on a test item and the testees' levels of performance on an general

evaluation of the ability the item was intended to evaluate. The theory was propounded around 1950 and 1960 by a psychometrician, Frederick M. Lord, a Danish Mathematician, George Rasch and an Austrian Sociologist, Paul Lazarsfeld.

Item Response Theory is anchored on the proposal that the likelihood of a right answer to an item is a mathematical function of a test taker and item parameters. The test taker parameter is interpreted as a lone latent trait. An example of such latent dimension is the general intelligence. The Parameters on which items in a test are portrayed by its difficulty which is also referred to as "location" for their location on the difficulty range; discrimination which is also referred to as slope, which represent how sharply the pace of accomplishment of test takers differs with their mental capability; and a pseudo-guessing parameter which characterized the minor asymptote at which even the low ability test takers will achieve owing to guessing which may account for example 20% probability on a objective test item with five likely options.

In the midst of other things, the main aim of item response theory is to give an outline for assessing how sound assessments work, and how sound single items on assessments work. The main universal application of item response theory is in education, where psychometricians apply it for constructing and developing examinations, storing banks of items for subsequent examinations, and comparing the difficulties of items for consecutive version of examinations in order to permit assessment among results over time as well as the quality of the items making such a test.

Item Response Theory models are universally known as latent trait models. The phrase latent is employ to accentuate that distinct item responses are taken to be noticeable demonstrations of hypothesized characteristics, traits, constructs, or attributes, indirectly

noticed, but which must be deduced from the evident responses. Item Response Theory is universally claimed to be an upgrading above classical test theory (CTT). For assignments that can be accomplished using classical test theory, Item Response Theory usually brings superior flexibility and offers additional refined information. A number of applications, like the computerized adaptive testing, are performed by item response theory and cannot realistically be carried out using just classical test theory. Additional improvement of Item Response Theory above classical test theory is that the additional refined information this theory provide allows examiners and/or researchers to perk up the reliability of a test. The Theory consists of the following suppositions:

A unidimensional trait indicated by $\{\displaystyle \{\theta \}\}$ (θ)

Local independence of items;

The response of a test taker to an item can be fashioned by a mathematical item response function (IRF).

Normal ogive curve and,

Know-correct assumption

Item response theory is made up three parameters models which are of essence to this study, these parameters include:

One parameter model: This model is also referred to as the Rasch model. It presupposes that response process is a function of only one parameter (item difficulty) and the ability of the testees. The one parameter model also assumed that guessing is irrelevant and that every items are corresponding as a result of discrimination. Its stresses that guessing introduces random noise to the data. The discrimination parameter is always constant with the figure of $a = 1.0$ for all items while the difficulty parameter takes diverse values.

The one parameter model is expressed mathematically as Baker (2001) gave the equation:

$$P(\Theta) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{(1.0a)(\Theta-b)}} \frac{1}{1 - e^{-(\Theta-b)}}$$

Where b = difficulty parameter

Θ = ability level of test takers

The a parameter is not included in the equation because it has a constant number of 1.0.

Two parameter model: This model of item response theory was named after Birnbaum (1968). Birnbaum put forward a hidden trait model in which the item characteristics curve takes the structure of a two parameter logistic distribution function. This model presumes that the likelihood of a test taker giving accurate response to an item is influenced by the difficulty and the discrimination authority of the item.

It is put mathematically as:

$$P(\Theta) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-1.7a(\Theta-b)}}$$

Where:

$P(\Theta)$ = the probability that a testee with that ability level (Θ) response to an item correctly

b= item difficulty parameter

a= item discrimination

1.7= scaling factor

e= exponent of natural logarithm

This parameter model assumes that there is also a zero guess work. The a parameter in this model is reflected in the item characteristics curve thereby allowing various items exhibiting different slope.

Three parameter model:

The three parameter model conceptualizes that the probability of a test taker correctly responding to any test item depends on the ability of the testees, item difficulty, item discrimination and guessing resilience parameter of the item. Guessing in this parameter refers to a situation where a test taker entirely lacking in the ability required for by the item randomly makes a correct choice of the response just by chance.

Mathematically, the 3-parameter model is defined as:

$$P(\Theta) = C + (1-C) \frac{1}{1 + e^{-1.7a(\Theta-b)}}$$

Where:

$P(\Theta)$ = the likelihood that a test taker with that ability level (Θ) answering correctly to an item.

b= item difficulty parameter

a= item discrimination

1.7= scaling factor

C= the guessing parameter

e= exponent of natural logarithm

Θ = ability

The C parameter has a range of $0 \leq C \leq 1.0$, although in practice the range is the Θ parameter. The figure of c does not contrast as a result of ability. Thus, the higher and lower ability testees have equal likelihood of responding correctly to test items through guessing.

Conclusively, the relevance of this theory to the current study can not be overstressed, as the theory presumes nonlinear connection between the latent trait and the observed scores; it also permits more fitting estimation of the true score; it can approximate item parameters independently of the number of testees being used; it also permits the researcher to pick items that are in agreement with a preferred model; and it applies and generalizes models such as reliability of the items, hence permits researchers to obtain more information about the measurement process.

1.3 Statement of the problem

The standard for educational assessment instruments for test purposes in Nigeria like other African countries has for decades been controlled by classical test theory notwithstanding its limitations in the provision of test takers' proficiency. This standard for assessing learning outcome using test instruments has lots of challenges in our educational system. One of such challenges is the calibration of test items in diverse school subjects for producing quality items. This problem arises from some educational institutions, examination bodies and their personnel who lack adequate knowledge, qualification and expertise in the development of quality test items instruments leading to poor assessment and judgment of test takers regarding their true abilities in a particular test. This is so because an assessment of the entire test instrument may not be able to throw out all the weaknesses of the various items that make the test instrument. The need to analyse item-

by-item in an instrument guarantees the quality of each item in order to make pronouncement as regards the quality of the test instrument.

Most teachers and examination bodies and their personnel ignore the various stages in item development such as item construction, item moderation, item trial testing, item analysis, item calibration, item sublets, construction of equivalent item, and item banking which invariably could influence test takers response to these item (Hattie, 2006). Examination bodies as observed are not interested in determining the dimension of a test, the items that are fit for testing, the sex of the students, the type of school students attend as well as the location in which a school is situated, rather they continually depend on the CTT of assessing students using global scores in an examination. Thus, if such global scores rather than the earlier mentioned parameters, are put to use in any examination-score-based judgment, such judgment may be unjust and biased.

In an effort to seek for solution to this problem, this study was designed to investigate the dimensionality and local independence of 2018 WAEC and NECO mathematics multiple-choice examinations as a means of gathering information with which involvement could be made to the enhancement of test construction and provision of quality items. This is supported by the alarming increase in the use of computer Based test (CBT), as objective test items are in most cases more reliable and valid.

1.4 Purpose of the study

The rationale for this study was to assess the dimensionality and local independence of 2018 West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) mathematics objective test items.

Distinctively, the study was designed to:

- i. Establish the dimensions of both 2018 WAEC and NECO tests items.
- ii. Find out the local independence of both 2018 WAEC and NECO tests items
- iii. Find out the items that fit the one-parameter, two-parameter and three-parameter logistic models of both 2018 WAEC and NECO tests.
- iv. Find out the effect of differential item functioning by student's gender on local independence of both 2018 WAEC and NECO tests.
- v. Find out the effect of differential item functioning by school location on the local independence of both 2018 WAEC and NECO tests.
- vi. Find out the effect of differential item functioning by the type of school on the local independence of both 2018 WAEC and NECO tests.

1.5 Research questions

This study is designed to answer the subsequent research questions:

1. Which are the dimensions of 2018 WAEC and NECO Mathematics objective test items?
2. What are the local independence of both 2018 WAEC and NECO tests?
3. Which are the items of 2018 WAEC and NECO Mathematics objective test items that fit the one-parameter, two-parameter and three parameter logistic models?
4. What is the differential item functioning by gender using item local independence of both 2018 WAEC and NECO tests?
5. What is the differential item functioning by location using item local independence of both 2018 WAEC and NECO tests?
6. What is the differential item functioning by the type using item local independence of both 2018 WAEC and NECO tests?

1.6 Significance of the study

The finding of the study may be beneficial to the students, instructors, test experts/practitioners, examination bodies, school counselors, parents, administrators and the general public. The study may also help the teachers in following strictly the procedure for item development as well as developing the items in ascending order of difficulty. This study is also significant to the administrators as well as the society at large as examination results may become more dependable upon which many societal decisions are now based.

The finding of the study shall serve to encourage the generation of items with attractive qualities for banking in both test's item pool. This may help the examination bodies in item selection. This is because from the variety of items constructed and banked, good and bad items may be identified through the use of item parameters. This method may enable the test developer or the examination bodies to discard bad items as well as identify good items for subsequent examinations.

To the parents/guardian, this study may help them in recognizing that it is not a sufficient condition to pass judgment on students'/wards performance after considering their total scores in a test; rather, the items in which the test taker responded would be considered important as it will possess the tendencies of revealing their areas of strength and weakness as well as give remedial advice that can create room for improvement in the students generally.

To the ministries of education, it may show if the present practices with regard to the use of global scores for determining students academic achievement should be continued, or another measures such as item response theory be implemented as a bases

for judging students' achievements. The finding of the study may help the administrators, educational planners, employers of labour, government officials and so on, to view and treat the examination bodies and their end products (graduates and certificates) as being qualified

1.7 Assumptions of the study

This study was conducted out based on the following assumptions:

- i. The test takers were all exposed to the same learning experience in mathematics.
- ii. Test takers' responses to the mathematics multiple-choice items are a true reflection of their abilities. Thus, the data collected is reliable.
- iii. That responses to the test items in the test are not influenced by extraneous factors.

1.8 Scope of the study

This study is limited to only public and private Senior Secondary three (SS3) testees in Cross River State. However, the study concentrated on investigating dimensionality and local independence of 2018 WAEC and NECO objective test items in Mathematics.

1.9 Limitations of the study

In the course of carrying out this research work, certain factors in the field or outside the field acted to influence the findings of the study. These include poor accessibility of study area, inability to cover all the targeted population, poor attitudes of respondents towards attending to research instruments.

1.10 Definition of terms

Gender: This is the collection of features pertaining to and distinguishing between males and females.

Item difficulty: this is the location of ability on the ability continuum scale of item characteristic curve (ICC). It is also known as item threshold.

Model fit: This involves fitting a latent variable model to test items planned to assess educational achievement, traits, attitudes, and so on.

Test: This is an instrument measuring a sample of behaviour. In this case, the mathematics multiple-choice test.

Local independence: This refers to a process whereby the response given by a test taker in an instrument is not influenced or affected by the response to the next item in the same test.

Dimensionality: This is a situation whereby items measure one and only one area of construct in a test instrument.

Differential item functioning (DIF): Is a process where a multiple-choice test item in a measuring (cognitive) instrument functions differently among two groups of students.

School location: Is a geographical location in which a given school is situated

School type: This is the ownership of a particular school. It could be government or privately owned

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter is based on review of some related literature and is organized under the following sub-headings:

- 2.1 The dimensionality of objective test items
- 2.2 Local independence of objective test items
- 2.3 Model fit of objective test items
- 2.4 Differential Item Functioning by sex and local independence
- 2.5 Differential Item Functioning by school location and local independence
- 2.6 Differential Item Functioning by the type of school and local independence
- 2.7 Summary of literature review

2.1 The Dimensionality of objective test items

A frequently asked question in education and other areas is whether a hypothetical construct is unidimensional or multidimensional. Many scholars have carried out numerous researches on the dimensionality of significant hypothetical constructs (Kerman, 2001). Such questions are indispensable to social science research since misspecification of the dimensions can result in erroneous practical outcome. Nevertheless, if a construct is unidimensional, using quite a lot of ways as disconnect independent variables would most to be expected cause stern multicollinearity trouble. Similarly, if a construct is multidimensional and a lone measurement is used, one would most likely only catch one dimension of the trait, which as anticipated would cause problem in determining what is happening with the trait and its interrelated variables. As Baghaei (2010) put it, “the dimensionality question is crucial to the integration of theory and research, because it

brings to notice the implicit theoretical assertions in any operational definition, and consequently emphasizes the need to include explicit measurement models in causal models.”

The improvement of assessment instruments in education, psychology and other social sciences discipline has the innermost goal of evaluating the common trait of interest, which is presumed to be a lone trait. Such a measure is referred to as a unidimensional measure. The dimension of the measure is significant for understanding the obtained score. Unidimensional measures entail only simple explanation, since all items on the scale characterize a single characteristic. In contrast, multidimensional measures require intricate explanation. Hence, the literature advocate that, in the first step of examination, instrument developers should run a factor analysis to establish the dimensionality of their measure prior to investigating reliability.

A number of researches have revealed that the postulation of unidimensionality is likely hard to be satisfied given that factor analysis tend to produce new promising factors that contribute to the explained scores variance. Some authors believe that it is tough to situate a lone factor when measuring a expansive ability or characteristic, especially when the measure contains numerous items with diverse levels of accuracy (Kamata, 2005). A lone factor can be achieved only when items on an instrument are similar: this implies that items assess related content with diminutive number of items, focus on closely defined content, and have the equivalent height of accuracy.

Tests and/or scales developed in education, psychology or social sciences habitually measure large construct that envelop diverse aspects of attribute demonstration. To accomplish this purpose, instrument developer amplifies the number of items to

increase the domain being assessed. In an ideal scenario, measures are allotted on the foundation of a lone measurement of individual disparity, but practically scholars often deal with bunch of items that characterize diverse traits. Hence, assessment in education, psychology and social sciences are complex procedures aimed at providing information about traits or some portions of behavior (Brunner & Sub, 2005).

There are quite a lot of factors that cause instrument to be multidimensional, in the initial instance, constructs in education, psychology or social sciences tend to be multidimensional in nature rather than unidimensional (Drolet & Morrison, 2001). In contrast to the natural sciences, which more often than not deal with apparent traits that can be measured using a solitary instrument, variables in education, psychology or social sciences are non-latent, and can be assessed using numerous parameters. Scales such as a test typically consist of a number of items contrary in the size of correlation with the quality, which in turn can contribute to the surfacing of new factors. These items in general should be discarded from the scale, but the circumstance becomes problematic when the content of items contributes significantly to the assessment of the attribute being measured. In such circumstances, the test can be regarded a multidimensional somewhat a unidimensional measure. Occasionally the surfacing of latest factors is attributable to assessment administration other than the content.

Ubi, Joshua and Umoinyang (2012) sample 800 test takers writings from a collection of examination papers of test takers who sat for the Joint Admission and Matriculation Board's University Matriculation Examination (JAMB-UME) in Cross River State, for the 2002/2003. The rationale of the research was to appraise the dimensions of Mathematics items by means of factor analysis. Result revealed that JAMB-UME test

showed five noteworthy dimensions and they noted that tests meant for selection of testees might not be solely unidimensional especially when items are selected from an extensive curriculum. Mathematics multiple choice items are developed on the contents which range from chemistry, physics, biology and even agricultural constructs as revealed in the measurement objectives for the syllabus.

They recommended that, given that it may not be achievable to set tests, predominantly mathematics, that are chiefly unidimensional, test developers particularly those in charge of collection examinations should attempt to meet the standard of item selection and development like ideal item difficulty, high discrimination and high option distraction values to balance for infringing unidimensionality condition.

Another study by McDonald (2013), he posited that multidimensional measures involve heterogeneous items while unidimensional measures consist of homogeneous items. Stressing that the multidimensionality of a construct could be surmised from whichever the item collection level or from the item level. The word multidimensional, as used by McDonald (2013) refers to the first condition, whereby a set of items such as subscale, item parcel measures a sub-characteristic. According to him, the most fashionable method of approximating reliability was developed under the unidimensionality postulation. Therefore, a researcher should apply item analysis to each dimension. In addition to estimating the reliability of every dimension independently, a researcher could estimate the reliability of diverse items collectively. Forcing a unidimensional scale method onto a multidimensional trait should be avoided, as this will show the way to biasing the result.

In another study, Bovaird and Embretson (2008) adopted two approaches of reliability in estimating the Coefficients for Multidimensional Measures: These are

reliability coefficient based on classical test theory such as alpha coefficient and latent trait factor theory which is implemented with factor analytic approach. Their results revealed that the estimates resulting from these theories are not too different. This view is in tandem by the fact that classical test theory is construed from common factor theory, which can be drawn from Charles Spearman's conception who described how to identify that tests measure a general factor and establish the quantity of error in test scores. The results also revealed that Alpha coefficient is lower bound to common factor coefficient. They are equivalent if the items fit the single-factor model with equivalent factor loading. They concluded that Factor loadings can be applied to evaluate item specific reliability, consequently, factor analytic approach is regular with classical test theory.

Spencer (2004) conducted a study on an assessment of the Dimensionality of Mathematics objective tests. The Mathematical tests were factor analyzed by means of confirmatory and exploratory methods. Confirmatory factor analyses using the LISREL VI computer program were conducted on correlation matrices among item parcels for each test edition. An item parcel is a sum of scores on a little subset of items. Item parcels were developed to give up correlation matrices that were amenable to linear factor analyses.

The postulation made in the parcel method was that the items comprising a parcel measured the same dimension. Another prerequisite was that parcels measuring the same construct were equivalent to each other. In this study, content area such as arithmetic, algebra, geometry, and miscellaneous defined the parcel. Within each content area, several parallel parcels, of 4-7 items each, were developed. Equivalent parcels were developed by forming parcels of approximate equal difficulty and variability.

The most important method used in the study, confirmatory factor analyses of item parcel data, revealed that the mathematics test editions were unidimensional. Simultaneous confirmatory factor investigations of the same equating section, administered to dissimilar ability samples, were also developed. These analyses were undertaken to test for the proposition of factorial invariance across samples. Results revealed that the unidimensional structure of the mathematics test was consistent across different ability samples.

Various added exploratory analyses were also carried out on item-level data by Spencer (2004). Full-information factor analysis using TESTFACT software was used to measure dimensionality within item parcels for one test version. Analyses were conducted assuming a two-parameter model and a three-parameter item response model; results suggested that all of the parcels were unidimensional. The results for the two-parameter model were more exaggerated by methodological pieces than those for the three-parameter model, signifying the need for the improvement for guessing.

Full-information factor analysis was also used by the researchers to measure the dimensions of the 25-item section in one version of mathematics tests under the postulation of a three-parameter model. Results of the analysis revealed that a slight disappearance from unidimensionality might be credited to geometry items.

Spencer (2004) also applied a third set of exploratory item-level analyses which concerned least-squares factor analyses of a smoothed encouraging explicit matrix of tetrachoric adjustment for guessing. Three sixty-item editions of the mathematics tests were analyzed, under two methods of scoring such as right or wrong or missing. In spite of the corrections for guessing and omitting, difficulty factors emerged, and held up across all three content areas, suggesting that factor analysis of adjusted tetrachoric suffers from

the same problems that have inundated most other attempts to factor analyze item data. The results of this study are seen as evidence that mathematical test is unidimensional. The result appears to be no empirical justification for reporting sub-scores based on content.

2.2 Local independence of objective test

Recent researchers in psychometrics have advanced from tests computation based on classical test theory to computing the parameters of a test using assumptions of item response theory. Among prominent studies are the relationships between item local independence and different performance levels of candidate in various items of any given test. Some authorities compare performance to some psychological factors that affect local independence like attitude, self concept, sex, to mention but a few.

Udoh (2011) in his research examined the degree of covariation linking test attitude and test performance in locally independent mathematics test items. A total of 189 subjects were sampled and used for the study. Attitudinal and ability test data were harmonized for individual testees by collecting attitude inventory according to the precise order of the student' seating arrangement during testing situation. The results of the regression analysis performed on the major variables of the study showed an important difference in performance across diverse attitudinal groups with reference to their different level of attitude.

Ayang (2004) carried out a study on item local independence and students' mathematics ability in Calabar, Nigeria. He adopted the survey inferential design, a subcategory of descriptive research design. He sample consisted to 600 students drawn from a population of 2,400 Senior Secondary Two (SSII) classes from all the post primary Schools in the

study zone. A breakdown of the sample showed that there were 50% boys and 50% girls in the sample. The schools were made up of 2 single – sex and 4 mixed sex. 100 students each, of male and female were drawn from single-sex school. The average age of the subjects was 16 years with a range of 5 years. Two instruments were used for the study. The first was a 40 –item past May/June WASSCE objective mathematics questions for 2002/2003 school session. The second instrument was a 30-items Likert type questionnaire titled mathematics performance Assessment Scale (MPAS). Results of this study reveal that local independence of mathematics test items have significant effect on the achievement of students in WASSCE objective mathematics test.

In contrast with this finding is that of Xiaozhu, Haigi and Chummel (2003). who asserted that when test items, for any subject, are locally independent, examinees' performance begins to wane. According to him, this change in performance is premeditated by a high degree of inconsistency in the attitude o examinees'. The implication is that student's performance across mathematics test items is significantly influenced by the local independence of the test items, which in turn influences, their achievement in the subject. Since, according to him, achievement depends on hard work through preparation, if students are aware of impending examination, they will work towards their success by serious revision.

Mandi (2012) separately studied “effect of instruction in mathematics” using special parameters of item response theory. The results of the two studies show that there was a striking straight-line connection existing between testees' performance and local independence of mathematics test items that were given after some multiple treatment

effects. According to these authors, attitude plays a vital role in the course of learning and must have affected performance.

In a similar study, Akpan (1989) examined the factors that determine students' response pattern in mathematics. The study showed that in the absence of external influences like checking, ability and nature of items making up a test, there is bound to be a significant straight-line relationship between students' performance and attitude towards the subject. A significant straight-line relationship was also proved in a study by Cohen, Bottage and Wells (2001) on the influence of response discrepancies. In this study it was shown that performance of students was significantly influenced by their response variability in mathematics. They asserted that it was as a result of the large sample size (of over three thousand subjects) that was used for the study, nature of the test statistic employed (ANOVA), that the results were as significant as they were.

Knoll and Berger (1991) carried out survey of students' performance in mathematics test which items were locally independent. A total of 1,500 subjects consisting mainly of students and teachers were used and performance test items in the form of questionnaires were administered in addition to the locally independent mathematics test items. The data analysis revealed that, students' low level of performance in locally independent mathematics test significantly influenced the item parameters.

Ogunlaye and Yemi (2006) conducted a study to find out attitude differences and its impact on performance of school testees in General mathematics and algebra. A total of 468 subjects were used. Two methods of measure were implemented, the first assessed number of locally dependent variables such as self-esteem and attitude towards classroom

atmosphere. A 2x2x2 analysis of variable was performed on various performance variables. They found differences among various attitudinal variable and performance ability in mathematics. Multivariate performance indicated a significant main effect. This was an indication that the subjects with high level of attitude regarding mathematics perform better than those with small level of attitude. This in effect means that subjects with high attitude in mathematics may be able to solve more difficult problems in mathematics tests with locally independent test items than students with low level of attitude.

Knoll and Berger (1991) in reviewing studies determining the correlation between attitude and performance-ability differences in locally independent mathematics items among high school and college studies established out that there was a little positive correlation amongst the diverse attitudinal groups, which did not reach level of significance.

Another study was carried out by Young & Keane (2011) to find out the influence of various levels of attitude on test item parameters (the difficulty index – P-value) on mathematics with locally independent items. In the study, attention was also paid to the variability in item difficulty index and response pattern. A total of 287 third grade high school students were used as subjects. The test instrument used was a four option 100 multiple choice mathematics test items. The test was administered in a normal classroom. The difficulty index (p-value) chosen was 40 or lower. Test of correlated proportion was computed. The chi-square (X^2) value for both tests for right and wrong pattern of response changes across attitudinal levels were significant at 0.1 level. It was found out that subject. Thus there was a major difference in response ability to the test item between high and low level attitude subjects (Students).

Ayang (2004) reviewing literature on Gutman's scale and the local items independency (i.e the p-value) of items explained that the deterministic model expresses the relationship between difficulty index and locally independent items in a one-to-one correspondence in terms of correct and incorrect response. He opined that item difficulty should be used as a standard parameter for achievement test, performance- ability and aptitude tests and that the same difficulty level should be used. He further explained that the tetrachoric correlation of item difficulty level of two tests should be perfect (1.00). However, literature on the influence of attitudinal levels on classical test item parameters are few and hard to come by, but from the few available, it could be said that students' performance levels have significant influence on test item parameters.

Ubi (2006) investigated item local independence, dimensionality and teaching trend of candidate's matriculation examination in Nigeria from the years 2000-2003. A sample of 800 candidates' answer sheets were drawn from the collection of examination answer sheets for students who sat for the examination in Cross River State for the four years. Four research questions were posed to guide the study. Tetrachoric correlation statistics was adopted to answer the question bothering on the local independence of the items, while factor analysis was adopted to respond the research question on test dimensional. The result of the study revealed that the JAMB-UME test items were locally independent and unidimensional. The study recommended that item response theory models be used in calibrating students' abilities as well as item properties.

2.3 Model fit and local independence

The violation of the local independence postulation can have significant outcome on test parameter estimation and on ability estimation. Research studies show that statistical psychoanalysis of data with local independence is deceptive. In a study by De Boeck (2001) which he mathematically displayed the effect of local independence on difficulty and discrimination item parameters. Their results revealed that if negative local independence is not factored out, the discrimination parameters of the mutually dependent items are miscalculated. He also revealed that the discrimination parameter depends on the difficulty of the item it interrelates with, but not on the difficulty of the item itself.

In respect to the influence of the discrimination parameter, the harmful local independence reduces the item information and the standard error of assessment is undervalued. The result showed that it is thus fundamental to ensure the precision of the discrimination parameters, given that they index the item quality and consequently the test worth. The result also highlighted some of the major causes of local independence, which he stressed that some of them are independent of the item's content such as external support which could be support from a teacher, tiredness, practice, item or response format, speediness (if examinees do not arrive at item 10, they will definitely not accomplish item 11).

Balazs and De Boeck (2006) conducted a study on the exploration of local item dependence for items circled around general reading passage for Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. This study was determined to detect passage-related local item dependencies in PIRLS 2006 cognitive data and approximate its

association with the nation performance. The analysis was conducted using the three parameter models. The item parameters were performed on a dataset that made up 500 test takers randomly chosen in the 23 PIRLS national samples. The result of the analysis revealed that ignoring Local Item Dependence can have grave penalty for the goodness of fit of a model, for the parameter approximation and for confidence periods. The finding concluded that the answer to any item is unconnected to any other item when trait level is restricted. The items may be exceedingly intercorrelated in the entire sample; nevertheless, if ability level is restricted, local independence signifies that no association remains between the items. This signified that achievement or failure to any item in a test does not influence the likelihood to succeed the other items.

In a related study Steven Ferrara and Huynh Huvnh (2001) carried out a study to assess local dependence in Educational performance appraisal with clustered free response items. The major aims of this research are to (i) extend to polychotomous items a methods to identify dependence in binary items that does not entail postulation of item response theory-based methods, (ii) investigate the enormity of local dependence caused by clustering of free response items around a topical mission or reliable reading passages in a broad performance assessment, and (iii) explore appropriate factors which may contribute to cluster dependence. The test was administered to a randomly assigned group of 3,000 test takers who formed the subjects of the study. The results indicate that although there is very little connection across clusters, levels of occasionally significant positive dependence exists for items within clusters. They explained from the result of the finding that a contemporary development in educational appraisal is to shift away from the fashionable

use of forced-choice such as objective test items and to rely more and more on free-response or open-ended items.

Such evaluations are often regarded as performance assessments or dependable evaluations. Dependable estimations are anticipated to reflect excellent tactical instruction and are understood by proponents to determine higher-order thinking practices and knowledge incorporation. In excellent instruction, instructors frequently present background knowledge and encourage relationship among strides in the learning process to make the learning less thorny. Correspondingly, in reliable measurements the test taker may be presented with a basis for implementing the assessment actions. The study also recommended that in adding up, the set of items presented may have been chosen and sequenced to pilot the test taker to a conclusion such as an elucidation, judgment, or suggestion and final phrase of understanding which reveals difficult thinking. In such assessments, open-ended test items are presented together and may be organized either approximately one or more reading passages or in a numerous-step assignment, in what the researchers submits to as groups. They concluded that Performance assessments that include such groups of test items may better appraise higher-order thinking and information assimilation than do performance evaluations which are non-clustered compilations of open-ended test items.

Similarly, Davis (2006) carried out a study to determine the effect of guessing and risk taking on achievement. He used a total of 156 undergraduate students as his subjects and a 50-item multiple choice as his instrument for data collection. The subjects were allowed a duration of 60 minutes for the test. The test takers were requested to hand in their booklets and examination scripts when they finish the test. They were then given a reading

assignment unconnected to the test. When all the test takers had finished, they were given a short item questionnaire considered to assess their comprehension of compliance with directions. The test takers were advised to keep their identity anonymous. The items in the questionnaire was made up of three multiple choice items which demanded the test takers to specify (a) their comprehension of the direction regarding when to omit answer to an item; (b) the methods used when uncertain about the right response to the item; (c) the regularity of the guessing relative to the guidelines suggested. The test takers were then supplied with red pens, their original test booklets and answer sheets, and asked to answer all the items in the questionnaire they originally omitted. They were also informed that their scores will essentially be based on the number of items rightly responded to in spite of the colour of the mark made. The test takers were allowed to work on their own pace until they had completed the task. The test takers were however not allowed to look up responds nor discuss the respond to items.

The test-taking behavior variables of the 256 test takers with the study data set in two ways. The improvement of guessing formula was first added to the items absent under the first sets of directions. Secondly, the ratio of accurate to inaccurate answers on the earlier omitted items was also established. According to Warm, the expected value of this ratio should be 0.25 since each items has four options. The mean score for the 115 test takers who omitted one or more items when approved for guessing was .665. This was found to be notably varied from zero at .01 level of probability ($t = 6.28$; $df = 114$). This finding confirmed that guessing resilience can influence performance, hence response pattern.

In a related development, Bao, Gotwals and Mislevy (2006) conducted out a research to establish the effect of guessing on students, achievement under norm referenced testing conditions. A random sample of 186 graduates and advanced undergraduate students enrolled in an introductory course in testing and measurement. The instrument consisted of 40-multiple choice item test constructed to cover vocabulary and basic terms in educational measurement. Twenty of the forty items on the test were legitimate terms taken from a glossary of measurement terms. The terms selected dealt with concepts for mastery in the list of course objectives. The test takers' tendencies to respond to unknown items were by interpreting the 20 legitimate items with 20 nonsense items. Students were systematically assigned to a criterion referenced or norm referenced test conditions by alternating the printed instruction sheets attached to the test. There were 93 students attached to each condition. Analysis of data obtained using multivariate analysis of variance showed that there was no important variation of students' level of guessing behavior on achievement between norm referenced test and criterion referenced test groups ($F_{4, 181} = 3.298, p < .05$). This means that guessing behavior by students has no significant difference between the two conditions and has no influence on students' test performance especially when the multiple choice items have five or more options. From this result, it could be said that students' guessing resilience in a test has no significant influence on test performance, hence, response pattern.

2.4. Differential item functioning by students' gender and local independence

The fact that there are disparities between men and women in different aspects including successes in academic work cannot be left without notice. Research carried out

within the structure of attrition theory has revealed that males and females within the Western culture tend to exhibit diverse patterns of explanations for their successes or failures. Generally, females often attribute their successes to outside factors such as luck and task difficulty while the males tend to qualify their successes to internal factors and their failures to external ones (Graham and Folkes, 2004). The authors also believed that contrary to widely held beliefs, though girls exhibit local independence by responding consistently to test items in the middle school and high school mathematics, the responses of the males and females in mathematics test items is virtually the same. However, females test takers seem to have less interest in the subject, and this may be a contributing factor to the dearth of females in mathematics-related occupations, particularly jobs in information technology.

Tennen (2005), revealed that when test takers run into mathematics difficulties, males are likely to credit difficulties to challenges inherent in the subjects using their abilities, while the females are more likely to explain response inconsistencies with lack of ability. He however, submitted that regarding general academic performance, females are more likely to attribute inconsistent response in mathematics to lack of ability, while males often attribute it to lack of hard work or unfamiliar treatment. If all the test takers do so well in their responses females are more probable to attribute it to outside help while males to their own ability.

Given the significant benefits of the study of test takers' response pattern, it is important that the differences in the response patterns of males and females test takers be investigated. Akpan (2002) suggested that one of the factors that would probably influence response variabilities in mathematics test items between males and females test takers will

be the stereotyping of mathematics as “males subjects”. Akpan noted that subjects like physics, chemistry and mathematics are usually seen as “no-go-areas” for females. Thus, it will take “divine grace” to persuade the female students to strive for success in these subject areas.

In a related research, Friedman (2005) in a study of the influence of sex on response frequency of lower scores among female students was higher than the male students in quantitative and spatial abilities. In the study, he drew a sample of 80 males and 80 females who enrolled for the first time in the college. A $2 \times 2 \times 2$ factorial analysis of the variance was used for the statistical treatment of data with the between subjects having sex of students, predominant sex referent in the quantitative reasoning ability and sex reference in the test items. 20 subjects were used per cell. The result revealed a significant interaction main effects between sex of subjects, sex of passage and items ($F_{1, 152}; 0.05 = 3.91$; $F_{1, 152}; 0.01 = 6.51$). From the data, though the statistical report was not significant, there were some interesting trends in the response pattern of the subjects. The response patterns of male and female test takers were markedly dissimilar.

Hamalton (2002) in his study investigated whether there was significant response variabilities among males and females in scholastic aptitude test in mathematics. The speculation was that since females have high verbal skills and males show extremely high consistency of response in mathematics, the females will likely show a significant higher response consistency on verbal aptitude items. The study made use of 391,154 test takers. Independent t-test statistics was adopted for the analysis of the data obtained. The summary of the analysis revealed the mean of 492 and 443 respectively on mathematics section with standard deviation of 119 for male and 109 for female test takers respectively. On the

verbal section of the test, standard deviations of 110 for both sexes were observed. Equally, the correlation between the verbal and mathematics response score were computed to show values which ranged from ($r = .64$ to $.68$ for males and $r = .65$ to $.69$) for females

In a study on mathematics precarious youth, Jansen and Glas (2001) found out that among the more than 3,500 males and more than 2,800 females in grade 7 and 8 who took part in his latent search in 2000 and 2001, more than four per cent of the males showed remarkable higher consistency to mathematics objective items. They interpreted their result as strong proof against the hypothesis that males-females differences in mathematics response proficiencies are attributable to disparities in the amount of formal education in mathematics. Jansen and Glas (2001) articulated that among the test takers they tested, males and females have presumably fundamentally the equivalent amount of training in mathematics that it was therefore apparent that differential course-taking in mathematics cannot alone explain the sex disparity in mathematics response pattern.

Comparing the attritional patterns of males and females test takers, Gray, Williams and Henry (2002) argued for an association of some demographic characteristics. Using studies with different sexes, they demonstrated that females tend to be more external and employs more luck attritions than males do. In addition, females often underrate their abilities. Thus females experience less guilt in a failure situation compared with their male counterparts.

In an experimental study, Bradlow (2003) investigated the influence of sex on response variability among test takers in mathematics and to determine the relative influence of item arrangement on response differences between male and female test takers. A 38-item objective test mathematics was gathered from items of the ACT university

mathematics placement programme to represent a range of items encompassing contents from elementary mathematics through college algebra. Three test form scores were constructed from the 38-item multiple choice test, easy, hard, uniform and random. 170 test takers who enrolled in three introductory statistics classes at the University of Nebraska-Lincoln were used as subjects. Three factors fixed effect analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used for data analysis. The result showed that the effect of sex on response variabilities among test takers was significant ($X_1 = 29.4$; $X_2 = 24.63$) on the total scores of test takers and also the multivariate analysis of response data showed a significant value ($F_{2, 158} = 4.10$; $p < 0.05$).

The findings may be sufficient reason for the submission of Lokan,, Ford, & Greenwood (2011) that most commonly used method of interpretation of scores for purpose of finding out whether there exist significant differences in response pattern in any testing situation between males and females test takers has been the use of same-sex-norms in which males scores are reported and compared to females norms. Knapp and Knapp suggested the use of sex-balance items which should be reported in terms of single norm profile.

Ekpenyong (2005) on reviewing literature on the effect of sex on stability of response pattern in mathematics observed that there is a stable response pattern among males than the females in mathematics. He maintained that differences in interest in the subject between sexes could be responsible for such response variations. He saw the need to blame the fluctuations of the response pattern on differential orientation of males and females that while males orientation are tilted towards mechanical objects and ideas, their female counterparts are oriented towards more of values and morals. From the empirical

findings of different researchers as outlined above, it specifically shows that the extent to which sex influences attribution and performance differ among test takers. This therefore implies that sex could also influence response pattern among test takers. There is need for one to be vested with this information for effective day-to-day test administrator – test taker interaction/relationship.

Gender is an identifiable students feature that might influence their responses to test items. Kelly (2002) noted that while a test taker's sex is not in itself a determinant response to test items accomplishment, the disparity in the response between girls and boys, predominantly in the physical sciences, is well researched and documented. Kotte (2011) contends that the differential anticipation and socialization that boys and girls go through are accountable for the gender disparities in their responses. "Concern over the societal status of women has been in existence for a long time, although the concern over low participation in science-oriented courses and responses to test items has peaked in recent years"

Ekpenyong (2011) in his study of adolescent groups acknowledges the supremacy of males over female students when he observed that on all tests boys obtained advanced scores than girls at 0.01 levels. This study confirmed there was a general superiority in the item responses of males over female test takers. But Bee and Maccoby (2011) argued that this observation cannot be generalized since females are likely to achieve at bigger levels in many activities later in life. For this reason, the two researchers reported that bulk of studies on representative samples show no differences up to adolescent period, but when sex differences are found in the age range 9-16 years the responses to test items tend to be

in favour of boys. They submitted that after this age range, these differences become somewhat consistent which could invariably affect their responses to test items. They however added that whenever sex differences occur in the responses to test items, there is the possibility that these results at least in part forms the sex biases and stereotypes in our society including those presented by our educational materials.

In a longitudinal study of sex differences in mathematics responses in some American schools over a period of 10 years by the Educational Testing Services, it was discovered that there is no sex difference in the middle grades responses but at subsequent higher grades. Males test takers achieved higher mean scores regarding their response consistencies with differences increasing with age level.

Ngban and Ibu (2009) wanted to give information on the responses of examinees in mathematics tests as it relates to student gender, their school location and the type of school in Bayelsa State. The intention of the research was to find out the connection existing between such variables as sex, school location, school-type and responses in mathematics test. Inferential survey design was deemed suitable because of its descriptive nature, as it involves the gathering of information to precisely and independently explain existing occurrence, which in this case was the 2006 J.S.S.C.E mathematics examination. The sample size of this study was 6000 students chosen by chance from the respondents of 12,436 J. S. S. students examination for 2006 in Bayelsa State. The state was stratified into on three educational zones and four schools were chosen by chance from each of the zones comprising 12 schools Means and standard deviations from the total raw score for each were evaluated against critical t-value of 1.96. The statistical tools used were the t-test for one sample mean and independent t-tests. The findings revealed that the responses of

Students to the mathematics test items examination was determined by sex, the mean and standard deviation for the males and females were 29.24 and 6.00 for males and 27.93 and 7.98 for females test takers respectively ($t\text{-cal} = 2.27 > t\text{-critical } 1.98$). The result revealed that male test takers responded consistently to the mathematics test items than their female counterparts.

Other research carried out by the National Assessment of Education Progress (NAEP) reported that in the area of science and mathematics, boys and girls demonstrated almost identical consistent response levels to objective test items up to age 9 and thereafter, boys take the lead. This report is in tandem with those of the "International association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) which in cross cultured survey of science found that differences between the response consistency scores of boys and girls were evident across all the 19 countries studied, with very few exception and that the differences were mostly in favour of the boys (Baker & Kim, 2004). Also in a separate study conducted by the (IEA) mathematics committee, mathematics response consistency was examined in nationwide samples from schools and found a clear difference, which favoured boys at a level. The observation that girls responded to the items below the boys in tests of science and mathematics achievement has also been reported by Shaycroft, Yen & Fitzpatrick (2014). The common characteristic of the various mathematics achievement data, they observed has been that the boys responded consistently to the test items than those of girls even at the youngest ages tested.

Consequently, the trend of these disparities has not been found to be consistent across subject areas, but it could be noted that in almost all the countries in which numbers

are available, boys clearly perform better in terms of response consistency than girls in the physical sciences and mathematics (Baker & Kim, 2004).

In another development, Ford, Greenword & Loken (2011) conducted a study to determine response ability in Mathematics among secondary school students. They gathered three sets of data for the study. The data were analysed using the Rasch measurement procedures. From the result findings, it was discovered that relationship associated with the responses in Mathematics do provide evidence that the estimated differences between sex and local independence are partly society-based. It was also discovered, based on the analysis of the raw scores across examinees and locations, that gender-based effects have minimal influence on the item responses.

In a similar study conducted by Stahl (2009) Mathematics response was compared between genders in the Junior High School. The result of the study showed a general decline in the female responses. Further investigations by Stahl indicated that the differences in the Mathematics responses among test takers were due to many factors, such as causal attribution, environmental factors and teacher related factors.

2.5 Differential item functioning by school location and local independence.

Location is the environment state around a school which could be metropolitan or rural. The school location is noted in terms of city and less city. Several research have explored the significance of school location in affecting learning products and item responses. Some of these research looked at location, planning and their attendant effects on the responses to test item as well as achievement of test takers (Owoeye, 2000). School location can influence testees' learning product either absolutely or harmfully. Urban

environment can be regarded as that which has high population concentration, comprising a high array of attractive common place views, while rural environment is described by low concentration of people containing a small multiplicity and secluded place views.

The result carried out by Somers, Patrick and Douglas (2012) on the consequence of school location on testees learning result III practical physics revealed that school location had a significant effect on students' cognitive achievement. The study revealed that students in urban schools outperformed students in rural schools in skills of practical physics. The investigator therefore, recommended that the stake holders think about enhancing the lot of schools in rural areas, that, with encouraging teaching circumstances, instructors will not decline their postings to rural schools. Also, if infrastructural materials and paraphernalia are made accessible as they are in urban schools, both Students' and instructors will be supported.

Jimenez and Vincent (2007) reported on the monitoring project for learning achievement, for five countries: China, Jordan, Mali, Mauritania and Morocco. In each of the countries, questionnaires were developed for the school teachers, primary six pupils and parents. Measures of pupils' academic performance included test of numeracy, literacy and life skills. Analysis of the data was carried out within each country and the analysis revealed that urban school pupils did better than rural school children in all domains in all the countries. In Jordan, significant differences were noted between urban and rural attainment in literacy and numeracy. The pupils in urban schools did significantly better than pupils in rural areas. In Morocco marked differences existed in the academic performance in all three domains measures. There also, the urban pupils did far better than

the pupils in rural areas, Jimenez and Vincent (2007) concluded that academic performance of pupils throughout the world in rural schools is traditionally worse than in urban centers.

Ogunlade, Obot and Anwana (2013) concluding a case study of three rural villages in Oron Local Government Area asserted that the Nigerian rural masses have been known and can be classified as disadvantage citizens who are living under conditions of deprivation from various spheres of life. This shows that student in rural area cannot achieve much in science and mathematics as there is no money to buy books and other educational materials.

Ogunlade, Obot and Anwana (2013) in his study of two large urban cities in Western Nigeria found that students from educated environment had better academic achievement than those from uneducated homes. In confirming this, David (2003) in a study of urban- rural background on student's performance found that students from urban areas have a higher level of academic achievement than students from rural areas.

In terms of facilities, Ogunlade, Obot and Anwana (2013) observed that the quality and quantity of educational resources and services in the school influences learning. She noted that in term: of facilities infrastructures and staffing, the Federal Government Colleges Could not be compared to State Schools while urban schools could not be compared to rural schools, This is because, in many Communities in Akwa Ibom State where this study was conducted, evidence of Several communities lack electricity, good transport system, communication System as well as several other infrastructural deficiencies which together retarded educational advancement in the rural areas. Mathematics and science teachers apparently in short supply generally refuse postings to these rural communities. Little wonder then, that this environmental deprivation and lack

of social amenities in the rural areas have been suspected to be the cause of the generally supposed low academic performance among rural students.

Akubuire and Joshua (2004) carried out a study of self-concept, attitude and achievement of senior secondary school students in physical science subjects in the southern Cross River State. Their effort was directed towards finding out whether any differences exist between students' achievement in physical science subjects with respect to their gender and geographical location of the school. They sampled secondary school students in third year from the area of study which comprised two hundred and forty (240) students each from urban and rural settings. A standardized achievement test was administered to these students with a 60 - item questionnaire developed to measure psychological variables. The study observed that the academic achievement of testees in the physical sciences was significantly predictable by self-concept, gender and school location. Findings revealed that schools in urban areas performed significantly better than schools in rural regions.

Evans, Williams and Williams (2010) sought to discover "factors influencing the quality of primary education in five regions of Tanzania by expansively evaluating significant literature and empirical data. The study was restricted to three districts in each region - one urban, one semi urban and one rural Available records and questionnaire were used to collect data from parents and school leavers. Observation achievement tests for all-purpose and local knowledge, and a battery of proficiency tests were administered on 300 pupils in each district. Analysis of the overall performance revealed that performance was superior in urban schools than in rural schools. The disparity in academic performance

between the urban and rural school pupils was explained in terms of the urban schools being better staffed with qualified teachers and equipment than the rural schools.

Educational research by Cox, Donald and Emmanuel (2001) examined "rural-urban differences in achievement, appropriateness of rural/urban achievement measures, effects of parents and the community on attainment of rural students, and how well rural students succeed in higher education. To accurately assess the small rural schools impact on students, rural/urban comparison was made on-students who were matched by origin, background, and access to information. It was found that there were little differences in the academic achievement of rural and urban students or in their desire to attend higher education". Also revealed in the study, was the fact that rural students aspired to higher education contrasted with proof that rural high school testees had less total access to educational data. It could be disagreed that rural high school testees were consequently, in terms of their general improvement, accomplishing more, not less, in spite of greater impediments.

In other research by Momoh and Uka (2006) however noted that testees from urban schools were observed to have achieved better in terms of response consistency than those from rural areas, They argues that the rural schools face problems that can lead to adverse educational results for their testees. One of such challenges as pointed out by Ertl and Plante (2004) is in terms of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) usage, which is usually deficient in rural areas. They however agree that these challenges could ultimately lead to violation in item consistency.

The availability of less resources in loads of rural schools than those in urban areas have been found to contribute to a more inadequate curricula being made available at

these rural schools. They noted that since the curricula could not be implemented fully by the teachers in terms of content coverage it will invariably affect student's response pattern which is a violation in the local independence of the test items. They credited the urban-rural difference in the response patterns of the students to factors such as an uneven distribution of resources, and lack of functional facilities. They also noted that the violation of item local independence could be attributed to some qualified teachers who are not willing to take up teaching appointment; those already in the system are not willing to put in their best in rural schools, for lack of motivation for teachers.

There are some suggestions that socio-economic status is another factor in any rural-urban difference in item response consistency. Socio-economic status has been shown to be positively related to students' non violation of local independence (Coladarci & Cobb, 2008), and there is a seeming disproportion between rural students and their urban equivalents in this aspect, with rural students usually having lower socio-economic status. Nevertheless, the role socio-economic status plays in differences in students' academic achievement may be less important in rural schools than in urban schools.

Alspaugh (2011) noted that a large percentage of the between-school variance in item response consistency among urban schools was associated with the students' socio-economic status, while a smaller percentage of the between-school variance in student abilities among rural schools is related with the students' socio-economic status. Community and parental contribution have also been shown to be positively associated with student abilities and succeeding item response consistency. Alspaugh however noted that rural testees may be at some disadvantage in contrast with

their urban equals in these respects, because tiny, secluded, and low-socio-economic rural areas time and again have less community participation in education which ultimately leads to violation in item local independence.

In another study, DeYoung and Lawrence (2014) conducted a study to investigate student's attentiveness as the causes of response inconsistencies among rural and urban students in mathematics objective test. They found out that students are usually attentive toward certain subjects or topics that appeal to them but show apathy towards other ones that they do not fancy. This degree of attentiveness or apathy goes a long way in shaping their level of participation in class and responses to the items in the subject matter. They however agreed that violation in the local independence of any test item is not evidence in attentiveness of the subject matter in question.

Hattie, J. A. (2004) conducted a research to investigate the effect of likeness on item local independence stressed that when a learner has extreme likeness for an activity, object and event, he interacts with it more frequently; otherwise, he withdraws from it or has as little interaction with it as possible. According to his finding, interest in mathematics could be evident from the way a student is punctual in class, paying attention in class work, assignments and tests, as well as taking delight in observing and exploring the environment. This likes and dislikes to mathematics as a subject could lead to a major violation in local independence of test items and vice versa.

Similar research findings from Amoo, Uhumuavbi and Umoru (2009) corroborates with the work of Anaekwe (2005) that interest plays a crucial function in the teaching and learning process. At the classroom level and beyond, learning can be meaningfully achieved within the context of optimal disposition of the learner to the tasks in

question. This means that the learner needs to be psychologically present and attentive towards the learning tasks. Situations often arise in which the learner may be physically present but psychologically absent in the classroom. Students that are interested in mathematics are likely to respond consistently to test items which is a non violation to local independence of the test items. There is no doubt that differences in mathematics attainment, in terms of school location exists, but Etukudo (2002) emphasized that differences in mathematics objective test response and students ability can exist only in the face of weak instructional methods. There is need for a superior instructional delivery process that could balance the urban-rural disparity in student's mathematics abilities and their responses to test items which conforms to item local independence. The study used games and simulations as a Pedagogical variable to investigate rural-urban disparity in the item response pattern and interest of students.

The specific aims of the research were:

1. To determine whether there is difference in the mean ability scores of urban and rural testees in geometry when taught by means of games and simulations.
2. To establish if there is difference in the mean interest consistency scores of urban and rural testees in geometry when taught by means of games and simulation. The result shows that interest in a particular subject matter could lead to revealing the true ability of students and consistency in their item responses which is in conformity to local independence.

2.6 Differential item functioning by the type of school and local independence

Private involvement in education could be demonstrated as a effect of collapse of the government-owned school possession composition and negated in the educational

sector owing to declining level of infrastructure and amenities, the abandon of government of the missionaries' schools after independence and the low spirits of public schools instructors on grounds of lack of structural welfare from the government with failure to pay of salaries. The breakdown of the public educational sector which reflect the declining standard of education in Nigeria with a considerable consequence on the student academic performance pave an easy involvement of the private schools which serves as a saving grace for the declining standard of education (Howell & Peterson, 2002).

The majority government-owned schools which are characterized by deteriorating structures, decaying building, teachers with obsolete information, examination malpractice, wanting in planning and non-motivated instructors will have a harmful effect on the testees academic performance as they may not be able to try to win with their private equivalent. This postulation is non-conclusive on the performance of the public school student as some still shine in opposition to all odd against their private counterpart.

So also, private school which serves as a amendment of the failed public schools tend to assist student learning and thus influence the academic performance for the student by making available a favorable learning atmosphere for the students and thus having a affirmative impact on their academic performance. The lone problem against the surfacing of the private schools is their rate of school charges which could be seen as extreme compared the mostly virtually free education in the public school.

The literature on public and private school efficiency on response consistency is wide-ranging and significantly international level. Coleman and Hoffer (2004), along with others such as Chubb and Moe (2007) and Bryk, Lee, and Holland (2008) provided proof that private school outperform their public equals in terms of test takers responses to test

items. Internationally, a number of studies using a range of techniques and data attempted to test the private consequence. For instance, in Indonesia, Bedi, Garg and Kingdon (2008) found encouraging private school influence on labor market earnings.

In addition, policymakers, parents, and other concerned people often suppose that privately-owned schools, on the whole, are improved academically than government-owned secondary schools and as such could violate the local independence of test items. However, this empirical postulation is not supported by evidence. Judgments by parents or policymakers about private secondary school choice are often entrenched in the postulation that, by selecting private secondary schools, families will advance the academic preparation of their kids. This impression of a optimistic for privately-owned schools effect rests on a body of research that advocates private schools surpass government-owned secondary schools in item response consistency (CEP, 2007). Current development around the world also demonstrate that many developed and developing countries are seeking partnerships between the public and private sector to share costs and enhance the prerequisite of education which could ultimately affect students' consistent response pattern to test items.

Other studies, including the works of Peterson et al (2006), Chubb and Moe (2004) and Coleman et al (2001), have established about the effects of public and private secondary schools to some extent. To them, private secondary schools tend to make better performing testees in terms of academics as compared with public schools which could be evidence on their responses to the test items. They study established that the student's responses to the test items in an objective test of any course or subject in private schools is

more consistence than that in public secondary school which is in consonance with the assumption of local independence.

Belfield and Levin (2005) investigated the effect of local independence on students from public and private school in mathematics objective test items. Their result shows that students from private schools are expected to response consistency to items because they attend these private schools and the foremost rationale behind is that these schools are usually very loaded in resources and facilities. Some studies have the view that school possession and the availability and adequacy of funds in schools do undeniably affected the achievement of the students in terms of their responses to the items.

Crosne and Elder (2004) observed that school ownership, provision of amenities and availability of resources in school is a significant structural element of the school. Private schools owing to the improved funding, small sizes, serious ownership, stimulated faculty and access to facilities and resources such as computers are likely to inviolate local independence of the items than students from public schools. These added funding resources and amenities found in private schools boost student's academic ability, their response consistencies and generally increases their educational attainments.

In another study conducted by Gloria Kivenule (2015) in Tanzania, the rationale of the research was to evaluate the reasons of inconsistency item responses disparity between government-owned and privately-owned secondary schools in Tanzania. Three research intentions were posted namely: to assess the grounds for private secondary schools to outperform public secondary schools in their responses; to compare the resources available in public schools and private schools; and compare the teachers' motivation in public schools and private schools in Kinondoni Municipal Council. A case study design was

used. The target population included 210 secondary school students. . The major finding shows that private schools students perform better in terms of their response pattern than public secondary schools students due to their employment of proficient teachers, improved salary for their instructors, availability of teaching/learning resources, excellent control coordination of school organization team (SOT), and good student's enrollment structure. Also the finding pointed out that the level of school administrators participation in decision making about the school issues is high in private secondary schools, teachers agreed in private schools have dedicated teachers, financial competence, good and experienced school administrators, and active inspectorate human resources. The researcher concluded that all the aforementioned parameters could aid item local independence by students in private schools and verse versa.

2.7 Summary of literature review

The review of literature for this study was on test dimensionality, local independence and the influence of demographic factors such as testees gender, their school location and type of school a student attend on the development of item and response pattern. The review begins with the relationship between the sublet of items making a construct and test quality, the relationship between a testee's proficiency and response pattern as well as other variables that could violate the assumption of local independence. From the literature, earlier researchers had suggested some best method by which the dimensionality of a test could be identified, such as principal factor analysis, the congruent test, vector frequency, and so on.

In almost all the literature reviewed, there were submissions to fact that objective measurement of true ability could only be achieved through a unidimensional test, though

some were not able to determine how it could be achieved practically. Similarly, most reviewed literature on local independence revealed that since ability which influences response to any two items in a test is constant, then the connection between the two items should not differ from zero. Other responses to these test items are affected by some factors other than which the test was intended to assess such as sex, the school the test taker attended, the school type and so on. Nevertheless, no literature succinctly exposed the influence of item model fit and differential item functioning in 2018 WAEC and NECO multiple choice examinations in Cross River State, which this research intend to unravel.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter describes the design and methodology of the study. The description was done under the following sub-headings:

- 3.1 Research design
- 3.2 Area of the study
- 3.3 Population of the study
- 3.4 Sampling technique
- 3.5 Sample
- 3.6 Instrumentation
 - 3.6.1 Validity of the instrument
 - 3.6.2 Reliability of the instrument
- 3.7 Procedure for data collection
- 3.8 Procedure for data preparation and scoring
- 3.9 Procedure for data analysis
- 3.10 Operational definitions of research variables.

3.1 Research design

Descriptive research was adopted as the research design for the study. It is a method which engages observing and describing the behavior of a subject without affecting it in any way. The features used to describe the situation or populations are usually some kind of categorical scheme also referred to as descriptive categories. The main rationale of this type of design is to accurately describe the features of a sample and to generalize the result

to the entire population. This design is applied because it entails partial coverage of the population under investigation and the sample is taken at random (Peter & Kenneth, 2018).

3.2 Area of the study

The research covers up entire Cross River State. The State was created on 27 May 1967 by the General Yakubu Gowon regime. Its name was changed to Cross River State in the 1976 state creation exercise by the then General Murtala Mohammed regime from South Eastern State. The State lies between longitude $7^{\circ} 50^1$ and $9^{\circ}28^1$ East of Greenwich Meridian and latitude $5^{\circ} 45^1$ and $8^{\circ} 30^1$ North of the equator (Falade, 2010). The state falls within the south-south geopolitical zone, a recent structure in Nigeria. The area is made up of three education zones namely: Calabar, Ikom and Ogoja.

The state comprised 18 local government areas, namely: Abi, Akamakpa, Akpabuyo, Bakassi, Bekwara, Biase, Boki, Calabar municipality, Calabar South, Etung, Ikom, Obanliku, Obubra, Obudu, Odukpani, Ogoja, Yakurr and Yala. It covers a landmass of about 74,425 square kilometers with a population of about 2.89 million people according to the 2006 National population census. The area is bounded to the north by Benue State, the west by Ebonyi State and Abia State, Akwa Ibom State and the Republic of Cameroon in the east. The area is favorable and useful for agricultural activities because it is mostly comprised of rainforest and freshwater. Most of the people are predominantly farmers, fishermen, businessmen and hunters. The mainstay of the economy is agriculture and cash crops such as cocoa, rubber, banana, plantain, oil palm, etc are available in large and commercial quantities.

The people are Efik, Bekwara, Ejaghim and Yakurr ethnic group, with an array of linguistic groups. Nevertheless, significant number of people in the area speaks Efik, Yala,

Boki, Ejaghim and Bekwara. The area is predominantly a Christian state since it is one of the areas of the state the missionaries penetrated as early as 1840s. These lead to explosion of churches of diverse denominations. Moreover, it is more a civil service state than an industrialized one and it is relatively peaceful and hospitable together with its enormous agricultural potentials which have fascinated people in every part of the country and indeed the world over to settle in the area, particularly the Calabar metropolis. Tinapa business resort, Obudu cattle range, the Kwa-falls, Nkarasi monolith, the Calabar carnival, Akachak festival, the old residency museum etc are some of the rich culture and traditions which serves as the tourism hot spot of the area.

Within the area under study are major educational institutions among which are University of Calabar, Calabar, Cross River University of Technology, Calabar, College of Education, Akamkpa, Federal college of Education, Obudu, Arthur Jarvis University, Akpabuyo, College of health technology, Calabar, and school of nursing, Calabar. The area also has many other public and private secondary schools both co-educational and single sex. Based on major learning institutions cited in the area as well as other key establishment like the Margaret Ekpo international Airport and seaport, the area is seen as the microcosm of the entire state and thus the most suitable area for such a study. The area is also blessed with abundant human and material resources, hence the hub of the nations' economy.

3.3 Population of the study

The population of the study comprised the entire Senior Secondary three (SS3) students in public and private secondary schools in Cross River State of Nigeria totaling 10,145 in the 2018/2019 session, who will be writing the West African Examination

Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) in the 2019 academic session as seen in table 1.

3.4 Sampling technique

Stratified sampling method was employed in selecting the sample for the study. Stratified sampling is a form of probability sampling technique characterized by the used of sub-groups in that the study area is subdivided into strata and members are selected to form the sample for the study. In this type of sampling, the researcher first names the strata of interest and then draws a spell out number of subjects from each stratum using simple random sampling technique. From the total population of 10,145 senior secondary school three (SSS 3) students spread across in the 549 public and private secondary schools in the study area, a sample of 1,014 students representing ten percent of the entire population was used.

The stratification was carried out in stages: Firstly, the study area was divided according to education zone. In the second stage, school type was considered, Thirdly, schools were considered along urban and rural area bearing in mind communities situated in rural and urban setting, while sex of the students was finally considered. To select LGAs for the study, simple random sampling technique using a process of balloting was adopted to select two Local Government Areas, from the entire education zone (South, Central and North) of the state making a total of six LGAs. The names of the 18 LGAs were written on pieces of papers and folded into paper balls and kept in three containers. Two folded paper were picked out randomly from each container one after another. This was done to avoid picking three or more Local Government Areas from the same region. The six Local Government Areas picked were used for the study. To select government-owned secondary

schools for the study, four (4) schools were selected by chance from each of the three education zone making a total of 12 public schools in all. The same method was employed in choosing the local government areas. In another development, four (4) private secondary schools were also selected by chance from each of the zone making a total of 12 private schools.

The entire number of 24 government-owned and privately-owned schools was used as the total sample of schools for study. The selection method was applied in selecting the sex of the subjects. Thereafter, 42 students from both public and private schools were chosen from each school from Ikom and Ogoja education zone while 43 students from both government-owned and privately-owned schools were also chosen from each school in Calabar education zone making a total of 1014 students for the study. The sample for the study is showed in table 2

3.5 Sample

The overall sample for the study consisted of 1014 students representing ten percent from the total population of 10,145 drawn from both government-owned and privately-owned secondary schools in Cross River State, as seen in table 2. The average age of the students was 17 years old.

3.6 Instrumentation

The researcher adopted the 2018 WAEC and NECO mathematics objective tests and administered to the students of interest. The West African Examination Council instrument consisted of fifty (50) objective test items with A-D options. While the National Examinations Councils instrument was made up of sixty (60) objective test items with A-E options. See appendix 1 for the instruments.

TABLE 1
Population of public and private secondary schools and SSS 3 students in Cross River State.

S/N	Local Governments	No. of public schools	Males	Females	Total	No. of private schools	Males	Females	Total
1	Abi	12	303	266	569	11	62	56	118
2	Akamkpa	19	277	262	539	12	78	49	127
3	Akpabuyo	6	41	36	77	3	14	12	26
4	Bakassi	3	23	28	51	1	10	13	23
5	Bekwara	6	109	113	222	12	52	36	88
6	Biase	18	195	171	366	6	16	21	37
7	Boki	30	281	261	542	17	84	62	146
8	Calabar municipal	16	246	441	687	32	121	138	259
9	Calabar south	7	273	307	579	23	108	116	224
10	Etung	12	54	48	102	5	11	9	20
11	Ikom	19	420	377	797	37	141	97	238
12	Obanliku	13	118	91	209	7	10	13	23
13	Obubra	19	445	366	811	21	93	78	171
14	Obudu	26	552	484	1036	16	34	43	77
15	Odukpani	15	151	166	317	7	11	13	24
16	Ogoja	14	98	121	219	28	73	84	157
17	Yakurr	17	388	262	650	27	91	74	165
18	Yala	20	197	179	376	13	33	48	81
Total		272	4171	3969	8140	277	1042	963	2005

Source: Secondary Education Board and Ministry of Education, Calabar, Cross River State (2019)

TABLE 2

Sampling Distribution Table

Local Gov't Area	School location	No. of schools sampled	School ownership	10 %	10%	Total	
				sampled	sampled		sampled
				male	females		
Akamkpa	2 urban	4	2 private	43	43	86	
	2 rural		2 public	43	43	86	
Calabar Municipal	2 urban;	4	2 private	43	43	86	
	2 rural		2 public	42	42	84	
Ikom	2 urban	4	2 private	42	42	84	
	2 rural		2 public	42	42	84	
Obubra	2 urban	4	2 private	42	42	84	
	2 rural		2 public	42	42	84	
Obudu	2 urban	4	2 private	42	42	84	
	2 rural		2 public	42	42	84	
Ogoja	2 urban	4	2 private	42	42	84	
	2 rural		2 public	42	42	84	
Total	24	24	24	507	507	1014	

Source: Researcher's field work

3.6.1 Validity of the instrument

Cognizance of the fact that the West African Examination Council (WAEC) and the National Examination Council (NECO) are reputable institutions saddled with the responsibility for the development and administration of examinations in Nigeria such as the 2018 Mathematics objective test, the researcher considered the instruments to be valid.

3.6.2. Reliability of the instrument

To guarantee that the research instruments (WAEC and NECO) were reliable, a trial test was administered to 50 senior secondary school three students (SSS 3) of Uyo High School Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, which were not members of the coverage area for the study. The researcher adopted the Kuder Richardson (K-R 20) reliability to check its internal stability. The WAEC instrument had 50 items while the NECO instrument had 60 items respectively. The instruments had reliability coefficient estimates of .716 and .702 respectively as shown on Table 3

3.7 Procedure for data collection

The researcher obtained a letter of introduction from the department of Educational Foundations, University of Calabar, Calabar, and presented it to the various schools principals/heads sampled for the study. The essence was for introduction to the various school heads as well as the purpose of his visit. The researcher with the help of other teachers in the various schools administered the research instruments to the students, taking time to read the instruction as well as explain some of the facts to students where necessary.

While the students were given time to ask questions where in doubt about the essence of the test, the researcher provided the answers to the questions raised. The significance of the test instruments was emphasized to the test takers and the need for

honest efforts. In addition, the students were instructed to indicate their sex, their school location as well as the type of school they attend on their answer booklet. The time as contained in the instruments was exhausted by test takers to supply all the needed information before the instrument was finally retrieved by the researcher. There was close monitoring of the exercise by the researcher and other teachers present to erase any leeway of error setting into the study with regard to the completion of the instruments.

3.8 Procedure for data preparation and scoring

The answers to the instruments by the test takers were used for statistical analysis. A key was constructed in which all the data received were coded. The research instrument made of two segments viz; section “A” and section “B”. Section “A” consisted of the test taker identification in terms of sex, school location and school type while section “B” was made up the responses to the mathematics objectives test items of the two examinations. A score sheet was provided in a person-by-item matrix format where all the responses were coded with one (1) for the right response while the wrong responses were coded zero (0). After scoring and coding the instrument, the test takers’ responses were arranged and coded in an SPSS and notepad using person-by-item matrix format. The confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and Bilog-MG3 computer software were applied to conduct/run the analysis of the coded responses.

TABLE 3

Kuder Richardson (K-R 20) reliability coefficient estimates of research instruments (N = 50)

Variables	N	No of item	Mean	St. Dev.	Coefficients
WAEC	50	50	27.74	6.30	.716
NECO	50	60	37.48	6.23	.702

The SPSS software was applied to analyze test dimensionality while Bilog-MG3 was applied to analyze local independence of the items as well as the differential item functioning involving sex, school location and the type of school, respectively.

3.9 Procedure for data analysis:

The technique of data analysis adopted for this research study depended on each of the research questions stated. The coded responses for test dimensionality were transferred to SPSS while notepad coded responses for the analysis of local independence and differential item functioning was transferred to Bilog –MG3 statistical computer software for its analysis.

- i. Question one: Which are the dimensions of 2018 WAEC and NECO Mathematics objective test items?

Analytical tool: Principal component factor analysis

- ii. Question two: what are the local independence of both 2018 WAEC and NECO tests?

Analytical tool: Tetrachoric correlation analysis

- iii. Question three: Which are the items of 2018 WAEC and NECO Mathematics objective test items that fit the one-parameter, two-parameter and three parameter logistic models?

Analytical tool: Bilog-MG3 statistical computer model (chi-square values of 1, 2 & 3 IRT logistic models)

iii Question four: What is the differential item functioning by gender using item local independence of both tests?

Analytical tool: Analytical tool: Bilog-MG3 statistical computer model
(Differential Item Functioning of both tests)

iv Question five: What is the differential item functioning by location using item local independence of both tests?

Analytical tool: Bilog-MG3 statistical computer model (Differential Item
Functioning of both tests)

v Question six: What is the differential item functioning by the type of school a student attended using item local independence of both tests?

Analytical tool: Bilog-MG3 statistical computer model (Differential Item
Functioning of both tests)

3.10 Operational definition of research variables

Unidimensionality: This signifies that items in the WAEC and NECO instruments measured one and only one area of construct. (Item 1-50 for WAEC and item 1-60 for NECO)

Local independence: This implies that the response each test taker provided to an item in the WAEC and NECO tests did not give a clue to the response they provided to another item in the same instrument. (Item 1-50 for WAEC and item 1-60 for NECO)

Gender: This is the sex of the test takers (males and females), as contained in the answer booklet.

School location: This refers to the environmental condition around a place where a school is situated. In this study, it is the urban and rural schools, as contained in the answer booklet.

Type of School: This is the state of having complete legal control of the status of a school. In this study it represents students who attended government/publicly owned schools and their equals in the privately owned schools, as contained in the answer booklet.

Examinees/Testees/Test takers: These were the Senior Secondary School students which formed the sample of the study.

Test: This refers to the mathematics multiple-choice items of WAEC and NECO instruments

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter is concerned with the presentation of results and discussion of findings presented according to the subsequent sub-headings:

4.1 General description of variables

4.2 Presentation of results

4.3 Discussion of findings

4.1 General description of variables

Results for the five research questions asked in the study were presented in this chapter. The chapter is concerned with all-purpose explanation of data; statistical analysis of data appropriate to each of the research question; arrangement and interpretation of results as well as summary of research findings. Principal component factor analysis and Bilog-MG were the statistical tools used in analyzing data for the research questions.

4.2 Presentation of results

Principal component factor analysis and Bilog-MG were the statistical tools used in analyzing the research questions. The research focused on assessing the dimensionality and local independence of 2018 West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) mathematics objective test items. The sub-variables include:

- i. Determining the dimensionality of both WAEC and NECO tests.
- ii. Explore the local independence of both WAEC and NECO tests.
- iii. Finding out the items that fit one-parameter, two-parameter and three-parameter logistic models of both WAEC and NECO tests

- iv. Discovering the effect of differential item functioning through gender on local independence of both 2018 WAEC and NECO tests.
- v. Finding out the effect of differential item functioning by school location on the local independence of both WAEC and NECO tests and
- vi. Finding out the effect of differential item functioning by school type on the local independence of both WAEC and NECO tests

Table 4 show the descriptive statistics of the total research participants used for the research and the number of multiple choice items in each examination. The table shows that the West African Examination Council (WAEC) comprised of 50 multiple choice items while the National Examination Council (NECO) had 60 items. 1014 students took the two examinations.

4.2.1 Research question one:

Which are the dimensions of 2018 WAEC and NECO Mathematics objective test items?

To respond to this question, the answers of the test takers on the 50 objective test items of the West African Examination Council (WAEC) and 60 objective test items of the National Examination Council (NECO) were subjected to factor analysis. This was carried out to establish whether or not a dominant factor existed among all items as it was anticipated that the examination would come out with one overriding factor. This factor would stand for the construct underlying the mathematics learning areas assessed by the test. A principal component factor analysis was conducted to establish the fundamental composition of the data. The result of data analysis in this research question is presented in table 5. The primary eigenvalues were greater than 1 which was adjudged significant. Table 5 illustrates the percentage variance accounted for by each of the variables. Twelve (12) factors had eigenvalues over the kaiser's criterion of 1 and in combination explained

19.26%. Thus, the first eigenvalue was 9.631 greater than the next eleven eigenvalues (7.738, 3.745, 2.758, 2.705, 2.600, 2.170, 1.770, 1.525, 1.476, 1.269 and 1.046) respectively. The first factor explained only 19.26% of the variance in the data set. The second factor variance explained 15.48% of the left over variance. The rest of the variance was explained by the other 48 factors with 10 factors each having a percentage of variance between approximately 7.50 and 2.50, then 38 factors each having a percentage of variance of between 2.10 and .08. The last 38 factors were removed because they did not add to a simple factor structure and failed to meet a smallest standard of having a principal factor loading of greater than 1 eigenvalues.

From the 12 factors adjudged significant of having initial eigenvalues of greater than 1, items 8, 13, 19, 21, 22 and 30 (numerical process), 4, 10, 15, 23, 42, 48 (geometry), significantly loaded on factor 1. This factor was consequently labeled “Numerical Geometry”. Item 2, 6, 44, 47 and 51 (geometry), 14, 24, 31, 36, and 43 (arithmetic), significantly loaded on factor 2, and the factor was labeled “Geometry Arithmetic”. Accordingly, loading on the third factor showed that items 7, 17, 25, 33 and 43 (statistics), 1, 2, 19, 36 and 47 (probability), loaded significantly, and the factor was labeled “Statistical Probability. Similarly, items 3, 12, 20, 30 and 49 (Mensuration), 5, 6, 18, 35 and 46 (Algebraic process), significantly loaded and the factor was labeled “Mensuration Algebra”.

Furthermore, six (6) items testing calculus, and vectors significantly loaded on factor 6, so the factor was labeled “Calculus Vectors”. Factor 7 loaded significantly on latitude and longitude, and the factor was labeled “Latitude and Longitude”. Five (5) items measuring construction and lucid, and vectors were equally significant and was labeled

“Construction and lucid Vectors”. Factor 9 loaded on trigonometry and Algebraic process, and the factor was named trigonometry Algebra. Factor 10 loaded on Calculus, factor 11 loaded on Arithmetic and factor 12 loaded on statistics.

Similarly, the responses of the test takers on the 60 objective test items of the National Examination Council (NECO) were also subjected to factor analysis. This was carry out to establish whether or not a prevailing factor existed among all items as it was anticipated that the examination would come out with one dominant factor. This factor would stand for the construct underlying the mathematics learning areas assessed by the test. A principal component factor analysis was performed to establish the fundamental structure of the data. The initial eigenvalues were bigger than 1 which was deemed significant. Table 6 shows the percentage variance accounted for by each of the variables. Sixteen (16) factors had eigenvalues over the kaiser’s criterion of 1 and in combination explained 14.33%. Thus, the first eigenvalue was 8.597 superior than the next fifteen eigenvalues (7.491, 3.964, 3.739, 2.761, 2.547, 2.440, 1.937, 1.873, 1.675, 1.518, 1.451, 1.365, 1.279, 1.221 and 1.144) respectively. The first factor explained only 14.33% of the variance in the data set.

From the 16 factors adjudged significant of having initial eigenvalues of greater than 1, items 3, 11, 24, 34, 49 and 52 (Logarithms), 8, 14, 28, 33, and 50 (indices), significantly loaded on factor 1. This factor was labeled “Logarithmal Indices”. Item 7, 18, 30, 51 and 58 (Statistics), 1, 44, 53, 55, (arithmetic), significantly loaded on factor 2, and the factor was labeled “Statistical Arithmetic”. Accordingly, loading on the third factor showed that items 3, 6, 10 and 43 (Algebraic process), 19, 37, 48, and 51 (probability), loaded significantly, and the factor was labeled “Statistical Probability. Similarly, items

49, 53, 55 and 60 (Mensuration), 36, 40, and 57 (Calculus), significantly loaded on factor 4 and the factor was labeled “Mensurational Calculus”.

Furthermore, 7 items measuring algebraic processes and probability significantly loaded on factor 5 and the factor was labeled “Algebraic Probability. 6 items measuring longitude and latitude loaded on factor 6, and labeled accordingly. Similarly, 3 items measured latitude and loaded on factor 7, and the factor was named Latitude. 3 items equally significantly loaded on trigonometry and loaded on factor 8, and was named “Trigonometry”. 2 items also significantly loaded on statistics which was loaded on factor 9, and the factor was labeled “Statistics”. 3 items significantly loaded on indices which loaded on factor 10, and the factor was labeled “Indices”. 2 items significantly loaded on set theory which was loaded on factor 11, and the factor was named “Set theory”. Going further, 2 items significantly loaded on construction and luci and loaded on factor 12, and the factor was labeled “construction and luci”. Also, 2 items significantly loaded on calculus and loaded on factor 13, and the factor was labeled “Calculus”. 2 items significantly loaded on vectors and loaded on factor 14, and the factor was named “Vectors”. 2 items significantly loaded on numerical process and loaded on factor 15, and the factor was labeled “numerical process”. Lastly, 2 items measuring probability loaded on factor 16 and the factor was labeled “probability”.

The second factor variance explained 12.49% of the left over variance. The rest of the variation was explained by the other 58 factors with 14 factors each having a percentage of variance between 6.61 and 1.91, then 44 factors each having a percentage of variation of between 1.70 and .044. The last 44 factor factors were removed because they did not add up to a simple factor structure and unsuccessful to meet a least criteria

TABLE 4

Descriptive Statistics

Types of examination	N	No. of Items
The West African Examination Council	1014	50
National Examination Council	1014	60

TABLE 5

Principal Component Analysis for WAEC

Component	Total Variance Explained					
	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	9.631	19.262	19.262	9.631	19.262	19.262
2	7.738	15.476	34.738	7.738	15.476	34.738
3	3.745	7.490	42.228	3.745	7.490	42.228
4	2.758	5.515	47.743	2.758	5.515	47.743
5	2.702	5.403	53.146	2.702	5.403	53.146
6	2.600	5.200	58.347	2.600	5.200	58.347
7	2.170	4.339	62.686	2.170	4.339	62.686
8	1.770	3.540	66.226	1.770	3.540	66.226
9	1.525	3.051	69.277	1.525	3.051	69.277
10	1.476	2.951	72.228	1.476	2.951	72.228
11	1.269	2.538	74.766	1.269	2.538	74.766
12	1.046	2.091	76.858	1.046	2.091	76.858
13	.838	1.676	78.534			
14	.766	1.532	80.065			
15	.718	1.437	81.502			
16	.692	1.383	82.885			
17	.652	1.303	84.189			
18	.605	1.209	85.398			
19	.542	1.085	86.483			
20	.502	1.004	87.487			
21	.457	.915	88.401			
22	.441	.881	89.283			
23	.416	.832	90.114			
24	.392	.784	90.898			
25	.364	.728	91.626			
26	.342	.684	92.310			
27	.330	.660	92.970			
28	.294	.587	93.557			
29	.292	.584	94.142			
30	.264	.529	94.670			
31	.244	.487	95.158			
32	.216	.433	95.591			
33	.208	.416	96.007			

34	.198	.396	96.403
35	.190	.380	96.784
36	.184	.367	97.151
37	.166	.331	97.482
38	.159	.318	97.801
39	.149	.298	98.098
40	.137	.274	98.372
41	.130	.261	98.633
42	.125	.251	98.883
43	.117	.233	99.117
44	.095	.191	99.308
45	.082	.163	99.471
46	.073	.146	99.617
47	.062	.124	99.741
48	.053	.106	99.847
49	.039	.078	99.925
50	.038	.075	100.000

Extraction method: Principal Component Analysis.

of having a primary factor loading of greater than 1 eigenvalues.

ii Research question two:

What are the local independence of both 2018 WAEC and NECO test items?

To respond to this question, tetrachoric correlation analysis was adopted to establish if there was any correlation among the items in the instrument. The tetrachoric correlation of WAEC result in table 7 and appendix 2 revealed to a large extent that the examination items were locally independent as most of the items correlated below .50. Nevertheless, there was high correlation among 20 items. These items include: item 5 & 4 (.687), item 7 & 3 (.618), item 8 & 6 (.696), item 13 & 14 (.684), item 18 & 12 (.828), item 16 & 12 (.647), item 17 & 15 (.700), item 21 & 22 (.681), item 20 & 24 (.616), item 23 & 25 (.693), item 20 & 26 (.788), item 21 & 27 (.676), item 20 & 29 (.611), item 23 & 31 (.709), item 23 & 32 (.829), item 20 & 33 (.628), item 23 & 34 (.743), item 44 & 38 (.742), item 50 & 41 (.653) and item 46 & 37 (.685). These result implies that there 30 WAEC items were not related and may not act as hints to responding to the next item in a testing situation while there was some items gave clues to responding to the next item in the instrument. This result also implies that the likelihood of a test taker answering correctly to an item does not depend on the answers given to other items in the same examination.

In a related development, the tetrachoric correlation of NECO result in table 8 and appendix 3 revealed that the examination items were locally independent as most of the items correlated below .50. However, there was high correlation among **25** items. These items are: item 4 & 5 (.725), item 13 & 12 (.687), item 16 & 14 (.696), item 11 & 17 (.813), item 14 & 16 (.665), item 24 & 20 (.648). item 22 & 20 (.828), item 22 & 21

TABLE 7
WAEC Tetrachoric Correlation

Items	item01	item02	item03	item04	item05	item06	item07	item08	item09	...50
Item 01	1.000	.247	-.092	-.078	-.071	.418	-.077	.317	-.077	-.106
Item 02	.247	1.000	.094	-.175	-.159	.246	.228	.345	.137	-.120
Item 03	-.092	.094	1.000	.333	.253	-.170	.618	-.166	.812	.142
Item 04	-.078	-.175	.333	1.000	.687	.149	.471	.184	.340	.154
Item 05	-.071	-.159	.253	.687	1.000	.200	.310	.316	.221	.098
Item 06	.418	.246	-.170	.149	.200	1.000	-.140	.696	-.141	-.093
Item 07	-.077	.228	.618	.471	.310	-.140	1.000	-.142	.663	.150
Item 08	.317	.345	-.166	.184	.316	.696	-.142	1.000	-.177	-.102
Item 09	-.077	.137	.812	.340	.221	-.141	.663	-.177	1.000	.156
Item 10	-.016	-.087	.018	.354	.392	.149	.059	.210	.026	.022
Item 11	-.067	.039	.111	.007	-.014	-.090	.072	-.071	.098	.164
Item 12	.027	.148	.049	-.060	-.094	-.012	-.016	.022	.017	-.045
Item 13	.079	.065	-.087	.012	-.008	.120	-.080	.196	-.074	-.053
Item 14	.099	.038	-.092	-.060	-.034	.186	-.118	.134	-.093	.003
Item 15	-.063	-.118	.077	.179	.103	-.004	.107	-.033	.085	.261
Item 16	.072	.148	-.010	-.062	-.068	.012	.008	.100	-.020	-.046
Item 17	-.071	-.085	.112	.098	.076	-.005	.025	.008	.113	.200
Item 18	.037	.168	.025	-.042	-.075	.012	.015	.032	.027	-.046
Item 19	-.103	-.089	.050	.160	.198	-.057	.088	-.045	.046	.214
Item 20	-.083	-.127	.138	.138	.116	-.077	.105	-.086	.139	.324
Item 21	.065	.122	-.093	-.072	-.071	.124	-.119	.131	-.106	.192
Item 22	.069	.055	-.079	-.074	-.086	.139	-.113	.160	-.086	.221
Item 23	.146	.132	-.125	-.117	-.143	.168	-.115	.119	-.102	-.103
Item 24	-.124	-.145	.132	.201	.143	-.090	.176	-.113	.140	.496
Item 25	.125	.168	-.106	-.119	-.138	.120	-.096	.177	-.090	-.112
Item 26	-.102	-.144	.177	.154	.124	-.089	.122	-.091	.176	.350
Item 27	.105	.140	-.093	-.073	-.085	.099	-.091	.113	-.072	.034
Item 28	-.133	-.062	.087	.101	.147	-.099	.104	-.080	.088	.288
Item 29	-.062	-.106	.158	.122	.086	-.099	.139	-.102	.166	.206
Item 30	.062	.200	-.108	-.092	-.104	.129	-.112	.158	-.105	-.027
Item 31	.101	.135	-.107	-.128	-.147	.108	-.106	.143	-.080	-.073
Item 32	.146	.125	-.103	-.131	-.150	.161	-.101	.112	-.081	-.074

Item 33	-.125	-.132	.117	.199	.155	-.098	.161	-.100	.131	.472
Item 34	.104	.153	-.103	-.131	-.136	.112	-.101	.161	-.081	-.089
Item 35	-.102	-.138	.181	.179	.136	-.075	.133	-.092	.181	.372
Item 36	.076	.194	-.098	-.126	-.145	.077	-.097	.105	-.078	-.091
Item 37	-.012	-.105	.082	.097	.048	-.057	.058	-.073	.091	.108
Item 38	.082	.228	-.064	-.114	-.120	.085	-.070	.113	-.056	-.115
Item 39	.033	.111	-.067	-.061	-.088	.098	-.066	.140	-.040	.124
Item 40	.051	.072	-.089	-.077	-.096	.128	-.082	.094	-.076	.160
Item 41	-.119	-.119	.122	.177	.127	-.085	.152	-.101	.109	.653
Item 42	.139	.068	-.089	-.055	-.068	.119	-.073	.154	-.060	-.025
Item 43	-.107	-.057	.159	.094	.066	-.087	.111	-.075	.158	.347
Item 44	.060	.201	-.090	-.111	-.130	.076	-.081	.111	-.048	-.118
Item 45	-.116	-.074	.066	.100	.119	-.097	.083	-.085	.074	.292
Item 46	-.054	-.111	.131	.130	.080	-.077	.063	-.058	.117	.142
Item 47	.095	.204	-.087	-.115	-.128	.083	-.071	.104	-.065	-.137
Item 48	.064	.050	-.058	-.017	-.024	.122	-.064	.143	-.051	.389
Item 49	.046	.087	-.065	-.122	-.114	.122	-.099	.074	-.080	.319
Item 50	-.106	-.120	.142	.154	.098	-.093	.150	-.102	.156	1.000

WAE C Tetrachoric Correlation

TABLE 8
NECO Tetrachoric Correlation

Items	item01	item02	item03	item04	item05	item06	item07	item08	...item 60
Item 01	1.000	.411	.140	.236	.236	.297	.140	.411	.082
Item 02	.411	1.000	.376	.306	.306	.337	.376	1.000	.068
Item 03	.140	.376	1.000	.426	.426	.406	1.000	.376	.043
Item 04	.236	.306	.426	1.000	1.000	.170	.426	.306	.092
Item 05	.236	.306	.426	1.000	1.000	.170	.426	.306	.092
Item 06	.297	.337	.406	.170	.170	1.000	.406	.337	.000
Item 07	.140	.376	1.000	.426	.426	.406	1.000	.376	.043
Item 08	.411	1.000	.376	.306	.306	.337	.376	1.000	.068
Item 09	.095	-.079	-.078	-.053	-.053	-.100	-.078	-.079	-.046
Item 10	-.034	-.037	-.024	-.018	-.018	-.031	-.024	-.037	-.078
Item 11	.001	.000	-.009	-.015	-.015	.004	-.009	.000	.011
Item 12	.000	-.020	.015	-.046	-.046	.014	.015	-.020	.014
Item 13	-.033	-.045	-.011	-.037	-.037	-.010	-.011	-.045	-.015
Item 14	-.010	-.009	-.073	-.010	-.010	-.057	-.073	-.009	-.059
Item 15	-.009	-.019	-.017	-.058	-.058	-.005	-.017	-.019	-.067
Item 16	-.016	-.017	-.048	-.020	-.020	-.023	-.048	-.017	-.063
Item 17	-.010	.002	-.018	-.034	-.034	-.016	-.018	.002	-.002
Item 18	.013	-.002	-.001	.005	.005	.016	-.001	-.002	-.034
Item 19	-.002	-.002	.045	.008	.008	.033	.045	-.002	-.109
Item 20	.000	-.012	.001	-.015	-.015	-.018	.001	-.012	-.015
Item 21	-.030	-.020	-.019	-.011	-.011	.003	-.019	-.020	-.003
Item 22	-.033	-.013	-.032	-.002	-.002	-.020	-.032	-.013	-.048
Item 23	.032	.025	-.017	.015	.015	-.025	-.017	.025	-.107
Item 24	-.020	-.031	.014	-.011	-.011	.034	.014	-.031	-.035
Item 25	.016	.018	-.025	.006	.006	-.011	-.025	.018	-.087
Item 26	-.020	.001	.014	-.011	-.011	.013	.014	.001	-.011
Item 27	-.038	-.029	-.016	-.009	-.009	-.045	-.016	-.029	-.007
Item 28	.050	.007	-.014	.017	.017	-.010	-.014	.007	-.074
Item 29	.022	.012	-.009	.023	.023	-.016	-.009	.012	-.038
Item 30	.016	.018	-.014	.018	.018	.030	-.014	.018	-.037
Item 31	-.032	-.023	.001	-.003	-.003	.002	.001	-.023	-.024

Item 32	.060	.009	-.022	-.004	-.004	-.019	-.022	.009	-.050
Item 33	-.008	-.009	-.007	-.013	-.013	.048	-.007	-.009	-.045
Item 34	.040	.032	-.022	-.016	-.016	-.008	-.022	.032	-.066
Item 35	.016	.029	.031	.018	.018	.010	.031	.029	-.028
Item 36	.038	.030	.010	.007	.007	.000	.010	.030	-.035
Item 37	.039	.018	.020	-.022	-.022	.021	.020	.018	-.075
Item 38	.039	.029	-.003	.016	.016	.032	-.003	.029	-.049
Item 39	.000	-.009	.015	-.010	-.010	.055	.015	-.009	-.043
Item 40	-.021	-.012	.012	-.003	-.003	.013	.012	-.012	-.024
Item 41	.049	.020	-.012	.008	.008	-.009	-.012	.020	-.043
Item 42	-.011	-.012	.001	-.016	-.016	.034	.001	-.012	-.041
Item 43	.077	.026	-.017	.001	.001	-.003	-.017	.026	-.035
Item 44	-.007	.015	.050	.027	.027	.047	.050	.015	-.040
Item 45	.024	.002	-.030	.000	.000	-.015	-.030	.002	-.045
Item 46	.010	-.015	.022	-.033	-.033	.056	.022	-.015	-.055
Item 47	.017	-.006	.008	-.010	-.010	.010	.008	-.006	-.032
Item 48	.011	-.014	-.012	.006	.006	.025	-.012	-.014	.007
Item 49	.013	.023	.001	.021	.021	.005	.001	.023	.010
Item 50	.017	-.020	.005	-.028	-.028	.020	.005	-.020	-.021
Item 51	.041	.040	-.006	.026	.026	.011	-.006	.040	.008
Item 52	-.010	-.013	.000	-.019	-.019	.004	.000	-.013	.017
Item 53	.068	.050	.041	.064	.064	.019	.041	.050	.043
Item 54	.006	-.006	-.016	-.011	-.011	-.023	-.016	-.006	-.050
Item 55	.031	.017	.007	.000	.000	.001	.007	.017	-.009
Item 56	.009	.019	.010	.005	.005	.023	.010	.019	.031
Item 57	-.013	-.014	-.012	-.017	-.017	.001	-.012	-.014	-.001
Item 58	.003	-.009	-.019	.000	.000	-.004	-.019	-.009	-.020
Item 59	.068	.080	.031	.038	.038	.013	.031	.080	.601
Item 60	.082	.068	.043	.092	.092	.000	.043	.068	1.000

(.684), item 23 & 25 (.700), item 20 & 26 (.828), item 24 & 26 (.697), item 38 & 33 (.614), item 39 & 33 (.738), item 40 & 33 (.700), item 42 & 33 (.823), item 44 & 33 (.732), item 49 & 41 (.725), item 52 & 55 (.611), item 43 & 32 (.761), item 50 & 55 (.744), item 41 & 32 (.855), item 33 & 44 (.732), item 38 & 44 (.679) item 39 & 44 (.697), and item 43 & 44 (.697).). These result implies that there 35 NECO items were not related and may not act as hints to responding to the next item in a testing situation while there was some items gave clues to responding to the next item in the instrument.

iii Research question three:

Which item of 2018 WAEC and NECO mathematics objective test items fit the one-parameter, two-parameter and three-parameter logistic models?

To establish whether the WAEC items fitted the model, a chi-square test was conducted on the data set using BILOG-MG3 item analysis computer programme to ascertain if the items in the test fitted the 1PL, 2PL and 3PL models. Table 9 revealed the result of the chi-square statistics. The chi-square goodness of fit analysis revealed that 30 items fitted the one parameter model, that is item 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 14, 16, 23, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41 and 46, because their residual variances were statistically not significant. With a 2-parameter logistic models, 33 items fitted the model, that is item 1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 10, 14, 16, 23, 24, 26, 27, 28, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 36, 37, 38, 39, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49 and 50, because their residual variances were statistically not significant. With a 3-parameter logistic models, 40 items fitted the model, that is item 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 21, 23, 24,

26, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 45 and 46, because their residual variances were statistically not significant.

TABLE 6
Component Factor Analysis for NECO

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Total Variance Explained		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Extraction Total	Sums of Squared Loadings % of Variance	Cumulative %
1	8.597	14.328	14.328	8.597	14.328	14.328
2	7.491	12.485	26.813	7.491	12.485	26.813
3	3.964	6.606	33.419	3.964	6.606	33.419
4	3.739	6.232	39.650	3.739	6.232	39.650
5	2.761	4.601	44.252	2.761	4.601	44.252
6	2.547	4.245	48.496	2.547	4.245	48.496
7	2.440	4.067	52.564	2.440	4.067	52.564
8	1.937	3.228	55.792	1.937	3.228	55.792
9	1.873	3.121	58.913	1.873	3.121	58.913
10	1.675	2.791	61.704	1.675	2.791	61.704
11	1.518	2.531	64.235	1.518	2.531	64.235
12	1.451	2.419	66.653	1.451	2.419	66.653
13	1.365	2.275	68.928	1.365	2.275	68.928
14	1.279	2.132	71.060	1.279	2.132	71.060
15	1.221	2.035	73.095	1.221	2.035	73.095
16	1.144	1.907	75.002	1.144	1.907	75.002
17	.996	1.660	76.662			
18	.956	1.593	78.255			
19	.867	1.445	79.700			
20	.770	1.284	80.984			
21	.744	1.241	82.225			
22	.664	1.107	83.332			
23	.662	1.103	84.436			
24	.641	1.068	85.503			
25	.576	.960	86.464			
26	.537	.895	87.359			
27	.500	.834	88.193			
28	.471	.785	88.977			

29	.450	.750	89.727
30	.448	.746	90.473
31	.412	.687	91.160
32	.396	.659	91.819
33	.382	.636	92.456
34	.359	.599	93.055
35	.347	.578	93.633
36	.315	.524	94.157
37	.287	.478	94.635
38	.275	.458	95.093
39	.266	.444	95.537
40	.241	.402	95.939
41	.222	.370	96.309
42	.218	.363	96.672
43	.197	.328	97.000
44	.193	.321	97.322
45	.179	.299	97.621
46	.173	.288	97.909
47	.161	.268	98.177
48	.149	.249	98.426
49	.145	.242	98.668
50	.140	.233	98.901
51	.133	.221	99.122
52	.118	.197	99.319
53	.107	.178	99.497
54	.104	.173	99.670
55	.085	.141	99.811
56	.067	.111	99.922
57	.047	.078	99.924
58	.032	.065	99.931
59	.027	.058	99.944
60	.016	.044	99.957

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

TABLE 9

Chi-Square Test of Fit in 2018 West African Examination Council (WAEC) using 1PL, 2PL and 3PL IRT Models

Items	1PL			2PL			3PL		
	Chi-Square	df	p	Chi-Square	df	p	Chi-Square	df	p
1.	53.9	27	.001	26.6	38	.917*	29.2	34	.703*
2.	25.8	27	.530*	30.8	36	.715*	33.0	33	.469*
3.	24.8	26	.531*	42.4	34	.152*	21.0	31	.911*
4.	19.8	26	.800*	38.8	34	.262*	30.7	30	.430*
5.	17.1	26	.904*	50.8	32	.018	24.4	30	.751*
6.	19.4	27	.854*	52.9	32	.011	29.9	29	.418*
7.	15.0	25	.941*	30.1	29	.411*	18.0	27	.904*
8.	19.5	26	.815*	27.8	30	.580*	22.3	25	.621*
9.	14.0	25	.961*	42.3	26	.022	20.7	26	.755*
10.	17.1	24	.845*	32.9	30	.327*	21.3	25	.675*
11.	36.3	24	.031	40.7	26	.033	18.8	24	.762*
12.	17.0	24	.850*	40.2	24	.020	25.5	21	.224*
13.	41.1	24	.016	58.5	28	.000	22.5	24	.550*
14.	18.4	25	.825*	38.5	27	.069*	11.0	23	.982*
15.	39.6	24	.023	52.1	24	.000	31.4	21	.067*
16.	31.0	22	.096*	35.3	24	.063*	25.5	22	.275*
17.	40.9	23	.012	48.2	27	.007	24.2	21	.283*
18.	37.0	23	.032	59.4	25	.000	29.9	20	.072*
19.	56.4	22	.000	56.7	26	.000	25.8	21	.214*
20.	42.5	23	.007	55.0	22	.000	38.4	21	.011
21.	42.3	24	.011	50.1	29	.008	34.9	23	.052*
22.	47.5	23	.001	55.2	23	.000	39.3	20	.006
23.	37.0	25	.057*	32.1	27	.229*	34.4	25	.099*
24.	45.2	22	.002	23.3	27	.670*	33.7	23	.069*
25.	43.8	26	.015	49.3	30	.014	46.4	24	.003
26.	33.7	26	.141*	31.8	31	.426*	23.4	28	.714*
27.	35.6	26	.100	45.6	32	.056*	41.7	28	.046
28.	28.1	26	.351*	38.5	30	.136*	29.6	26	.283*
29.	22.6	25	.601*	51.5	34	.027	30.5	30	.438*
30.	26.2	25	.398*	35.9	33	.334*	28.6	29	.484*
31.	24.0	27	.632*	46.2	33	.062*	37.0	29	.145*

32. 22.0	24	.580*	35.8	33	.337*	26.4	29	.602*
33. 21.3	26	.726*	45.2	35	.115*	39.0	29	.101*
34. 22.5	24	.546*	26.4	34	.821*	31.2	28	.307*
35. 26.9	26	.412*	57.3	35	.010	39.8	31	.133*
36. 22.2	27	.728*	35.9	35	.426*	48.6	33	.038
37. 34.3	27	.156*	47.8	35	.073*	41.2	33	.154*
38. 17.8	28	.931*	32.0	35	.612*	30.0	34	.661*
39. 39.5	28	.073*	38.0	34	.293*	28.8	36	.798*
40. 26.1	29	.618*	52.0	36	.041	41.2	33	.155*
41. 40.3	28	.062*	51.4	37	.058*	24.6	34	.881*
42. 40.1	27	.020	33.1	34	.513*	38.6	36	.354*
43. 50.9	28	.005	31.7	39	.792*	41.3	37	.287*
44. 42.1	27	.032	45.0	36	.145*	48.7	33	.038
45. 53.4	29	.003	40.7	42	.528*	49.9	39	.112*
46. 39.3	28	.076*	50.1	40	.130*	45.9	39	.208*
47. 89.3	29	.000	35.7	42	.741*	58.2	39	.024
48. 53.1	28	.002	27.7	40	.930*	58.5	39	.023
49. 69.9	29	.000	39.7	42	.571*	58.4	39	.023
50. 76.7	28	.000	51.3	41	.130*	84.2	39	.000

The result in table 9 also revealed that 40 items representing 80% of the WAEC test was considered good items and the remaining 10 items representing 20% of the test were indicative of bad items and were required to be revised dropped from the test.

Similarly, to establish whether the NECO items fitted the model, a chi-square test was also conducted on the data set by means of BILOG-MG3 item analysis computer programme to ascertain whether the items fitted the 1PL, 2PL and 3PL models. Table 10 revealed the results of the chi-square statistics. The chi-square goodness of fit analysis showed that With a 1-parameter logistic models, 33 items fitted the model, that is item 1, 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 10, 14, 16, 23, 24, 26, 27, 28, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 36, 37, 38, 39, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49 and 50, because their residual variances were statistically not significant. The result also showed that 41 items fitted the 2-parameter model, that is item 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 22, 24, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49 and 50, because their residual variances were statistically not significant.

With a 3-parameter logistic models, 41 items also fitted the model, that is item 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 22, 24, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49 and 50, because their residual variances were also statistically not significant. The result in table 10 also revealed that 41 items representing 68.3% of the NECO test was considered good items and the remaining 19 items representing 31.7% of the test were indicative of bad items and were required to be revised dropped from the test.

TABLE 10

Chi-Square Test of Fit in 2018 National Examination Council (NECO) using 1PL, 2PL and 3PL IRT Models

Items	1PL			2PL			3PL		
	Chi-Square	df	p	Chi-Square	df	p	Chi-Square	df	p
1.	56.7	28	.321*	59.2	56	.030	72.1	51	.027
2.	39.5	28	.072*	50.5	54	.609*	45.9	47	.516*
3.	31.6	30	.385*	55.0	52	.362*	62.3	49	.096*
4.	25.4	28	.607*	66.1	50	.063*	52.8	50	.366*
5.	26.0	28	.032	42.8	50	.021	76.1	45	.002
6.	33.0	30	.011	56.9	53	.331*	61.2	49	.113*
7.	14.5	29	.988*	46.6	50	.019	66.0	41	.007
8.	37.8	29	.126*	41.6	48	.731*	51.3	43	.179*
9.	18.9	29	.021	43.4	47	.034	79.4	46	.001
10.	25.6	30	.696*	53.4	48	.044	73.0	42	.002
11.	31.4	30	.028	56.7	54	.376*	45.7	52	.718*
12.	43.1	30	.043	33.4	54	.987*	55.9	47	.174*
13.	45.7	30	.032	62.6	60	.383*	50.5	57	.714*
14.	30.5	30	.441*	38.8	53	.927*	55.7	50	.268*
15.	23.8	29	.006	50.9	51	.476*	46.2	45	.422*
16.	27.1	30	.615*	33.2	51	.975*	52.2	49	.351*
17.	25.4	30	.021	39.8	52	.892*	48.2	49	.506*
18.	33.0	29	.001	54.2	49	.281*	52.9	49	.325*
19.	31.6	30	.024	47.4	51	.616*	52.1	49	.353*
20.	37.1	30	.033	45.8	53	.748*	57.8	46	.113*
21.	30.1	31	.042	87.4	67	.048	97.6	67	.008
22.	29.5	30	.023	50.7	51	.486*	60.4	45	.062*
23.	26.8	28	.528*	51.9	49	.032	70.4	46	.011
24.	32.8	30	.332*	34.6	49	.940*	56.6	47	.160*
25.	22.1	30	.028	35.6	47	.021	60.8	42	.030
26.	22.7	29	.790*	44.7	49	.647*	44.1	46	.552*
27.	33.5	29	.258*	41.9	43	.520*	50.4	41	.149*
28.	26.3	29	.610*	44.5	46	.535*	44.3	46	.544*
29.	37.6	28	.030	48.6	46	.367*	48.2	43	.269*
30.	29.8	29	.422*	34.1	49	.947*	49.8	43	.220*
31.	45.3	29	.087*	39.0	43	.646*	36.2	47	.872*
32.	58.3	30	.213*	42.8	59	.011	82.4	57	.015
33.	52.6	28	.346*	43.6	43	.447*	47.3	41	.229*
34.	25.0	30	.726*	40.1	52	.884*	57.2	42	.059*

35. 43.8	29	.381*	32.0	47	.953*	36.0	42	.731*
36. 21.6	30	.867*	50.8	50	.442*	61.6	47	.074*
37. 35.1	29	.200*	46.8	46	.439*	40.2	44	.634*
38. 27.8	28	.477*	62.7	49	.090*	50.0	45	.281*
39. 34.6	30	.259*	24.3	48	.998*	43.7	44	.484*
40. 55.5	28	.001	50.2	49	.425*	58.2	45	.089*
41. 41.7	28	.062*	42.2	51	.806*	48.2	48	.464*
42. 37.8	29	.127*	60.2	55	.294*	52.9	50	.361*
43. 41.6	29	.060*	44.6	54	.816*	45.4	51	.694*
44. 32.0	30	.367*	54.4	55	.499*	40.9	51	.842*
45. 36.7	30	.187*	56.9	58	.516*	54.5	56	.532*
46. 41.9	30	.073*	45.6	56	.839*	46.7	52	.681*
47. 29.7	29	.427*	47.8	55	.744*	58.4	57	.425*
48. 50.3	28	.643*	64.3	58	.266*	49.4	56	.721*
49. 35.8	30	.215*	62.0	57	.301*	61.9	54	.214*
50. 53.0	30	.112*	44.6	62	.953*	34.8	57	.991*
51. 44.3	30	.044	173.5	73	.000	176.4	66	.000
52. 47.3	31	.030	216.9	75	.000	204.0	68	.000
53. 58.9	31	.001	177.7	72	.000	177.0	70	.000
54. 45.6	31	.043	234.8	72	.000	192.0	66	.000
55. 69.7	31	.000	186.7	75	.000	182.2	68	.000
56. 51.4	30	.008	201.1	73	.000	199.8	67	.000
57. 62.4	31	.000	190.2	72	.000	170.8	65	.000
58. 43.1	30	.007	188.8	75	.000	183.7	68	.000
59. 63.3	31	.000	148.1	73	.000	158.9	73	.000
60. 88.0	29	.000	119.8	75	.008	122.7	67	.000

iv Research question four:

What is the differential item functioning by gender using item local independence of both WAEC and NECO tests?

To determine gender influence on the responses of WAEC multiple choice items, a Differential Item Functioning (DIF) was conducted on the data set using BILOG-MG3 item analysis computer programme to ascertain whether the male students were superior in their abilities as compared to their female equals. Table 11 showed the results of the responses. The result revealed that there was no major disparity between the male and female testees regarding their abilities on responding to the test items. The test revealed that male students had superior abilities on 27 items while their female counterparts had superior abilities on 22 item items. It can be observe from the result that the males had superior abilities than their female counterparts on item one (1) with ability difference of (.031), item 3 (.047), item 5 (.041), item 6 (.063), item 9 (.056), item 10 (.024), item 11 (.167), item 12 (.035), item 15 (.092), item 17 (.106), item 18, (.005), item 19 (.068), item 20 (.049), item 21 (.037), item 23 (.015), item 31 (.064), item 34 (.019), item 36 (.079), item 38 (.022), item 39 (.055), item 40 (.062), item 41 (.043), item 43 (.021), item 45 (.049), item 47 (.029), item 48 (.005) and item 50 (.017).

Similarly, their female counterparts had superior abilities on 22 items than the males. These items includes 2 (.093), item 4 (.051), item 8 (.042), item 13 (.106), item 14 (.005), item 16 (.033), item 22 (.034), item 24 (.020), item 25 (.054), item 26 (.078), item

27 (.048), item 28 (.019), item 29 (.056), item 30 (.118), item 32 (.178), item 33 (.057), item 35 (.027), item 37 (.055), item 42 (.022), item 44 (.026), item 46 (.024), and item 49 (.02).

TABLE 11

Differential Item Functioning (DIF) of 2018 West African Examination Council (WAEC) multiple-choice item responses based on student's sex

Items	Threshold			Items	Threshold		
	Males	Females	Difference		Males	Females	Difference
1.	-0.832	-0.801	0.031	31	-1.001	-0.937	0.064
2.	0.857	0.950	-0.093	32	-0.902	-1.081	-0.178
3.	-0.950	-0.903	0.047	33	0.911	0.968	-0.057
4.	-0.890	-0.941	-0.051	34	-0.991	-0.972	0.019
5.	0.991	0.950	0.041	35	-0.924	-0.950	-0.027
6.	-0.996	-0.933	0.063	36	-0.946	-1.025	0.079
7.	-1.039	-1.039	0.000	37	-0.886	-0.941	-0.055
8.	-0.968	-1.010	-0.042	38	0.955	0.932	0.023
9.	-1.085	-1.029	0.056	39	0.937	0.882	0.055
10.	-1.024	-1.000	0.024	40	0.973	0.911	0.062
11.	-1.113	-0.946	0.167	41	0.937	0.894	0.043
12.	-1.064	-1.029	0.035	42	0.928	0.951	-0.022
13.	-0.996	-1.102	-0.106	43	0.865	0.844	0.021
14.	-1.019	-1.025	-0.005	44	0.924	0.950	-0.026
15.	1.102	1.010	0.092	45	0.825	0.776	0.049
16.	-0.991	-1.024	-0.033	46	0.857	0.882	-0.024
17.	-1.102	-0.996	0.106	47	0.770	0.741	0.029
18.	-1.010	-1.005	0.005	48	0.845	0.840	0.005
19.	-1.049	-0.982	0.068	49	0.733	0.758	-0.025
20.	1.054	1.005	0.049	50	-0.793	-0.776	0.017
21.	-0.996	-0.959	0.037				
22.	1.015	1.049	-0.034				
23.	-1.015	-1.000	0.015				
24.	1.024	1.044	-0.020				
25.	1.005	1.059	-0.054				
26.	0.982	1.059	-0.078				
27.	-0.982	-1.029	-0.048				
28.	-1.005	-1.025	-0.019				
29.	-0.959	-1.015	-0.056				
30.	-0.941	-1.060	-0.118				

However, there was no disparity in ability between the male and female students on item 7.

Similarly, to determine gender influence on the responses of NECO multiple choice items, a Differential Item Functioning (DIF) was conducted on the data via BILOG-MG3 item analysis computer programme to ascertain whether the male students were superior in their abilities as compared to their female equivalent. Table 12 showed the results of the responses. The result shows that there was major difference between the male and female students regarding their abilities on responding to the test items. The test revealed that male students had superior abilities on 43 items while their female counterparts had superior abilities on only 17 item items. It can also be observe from the result that the males had superior abilities than their female counterparts on item one (1) with ability difference of (.216), item 2 (.191), item 3 (.324), item 4 (.057), item 5 (.185), item 10 (.024), item 12 (.041), item 13 (.026), item 14 (.041), item 16 (.250), item 20 (.041), item 22 (.158), item 25 (.187), item 26 (.154), item 27 (.170), item 28 (.267), item 29 (.312), item 30 (.243), item 31 (.118), item 32 (.158), item 33 (.056), item 34 (.088), item 35 (.120), item 39 (.009), item 41 (.063), item 42 (.079), item 43 (.114), item 44 (.118), item 45 (.141), item 46 (.017), item 47 (.263), item 48 (.011), item 49 (.081), item 51 (.127), item 52 (.042), item 53 (.013), item 54 (.165), item 55 (.083), item 56 (.285), item 57 (.069), item 58 (.101), item 59 (.022) and item 60 (0.055)

Similarly, their female counterparts had superior abilities on 17 items than the males. These items includes item 6 (-0.070), item 7 (-0.173), item 8 (-0.224), item 9 (-0.046), item 11 (-0.038), item 15 (-0.324), item 17 (-0.022), item 18 (-0.135), item 19

TABLE 12

Differential Item Functioning (DIF) on the 2018 National Examination Council (NECO) multiple-choice item responses based on student's sex

Items	Threshold			Items	Threshold		
	Males	Females	Difference		Males	Females	Difference
1.	-1.884	-1.668	0.216	31	-1.755	-1.637	0.118
2.	-1.985	-1.794	0.191	32	-1.239	-1.082	0.158
3.	-2.054	-1.730	0.324	33	-1.755	-1.699	0.056
4.	-1.884	-1.826	0.057	34	-1.802	-1.714	0.088
5.	-2.145	-1.960	0.185	35	-1.834	-1.714	0.120
6.	-1.724	-1.794	-0.070	36	-1.588	-1.730	-0.142
7.	-1.985	-2.158	-0.173	37	-1.632	-1.875	-0.243
8.	-1.934	-2.158	-0.224	38	-1.573	-1.607	-0.034
9.	-2.002	-2.048	-0.046	39	-1.818	-1.810	0.009
10.	-2.002	-1.977	0.024	40	-1.662	-1.668	-0.005
11.	-1.739	-1.778	-0.038	41	-1.544	-1.607	0.063
12.	-1.802	-1.762	0.041	42	-1.558	-1.637	0.079
13.	-1.430	-1.404	0.026	43	-1.360	-1.475	0.114
14.	-1.771	-1.730	0.041	44	-1.444	-1.562	0.118
15.	-1.724	-2.048	-0.324	45	-1.320	-1.460	0.141
16.	-1.934	-1.683	0.250	46	-1.458	-1.475	0.017
17.	-1.739	-1.762	-0.022	47	-1.226	-1.489	0.263
18.	-1.724	-1.859	-0.135	48	-1.558	-1.547	0.011
19.	-1.678	-1.762	-0.084	49	-1.253	-1.334	0.081
20.	-1.755	-1.714	0.041	50	-1.293	-1.472	-0.179
21.	-0.660	-0.772	-0.112	51	-0.352	-0.479	0.127
22.	-1.967	-1.810	0.158	52	-0.567	-0.525	0.042
23.	-1.632	-1.777	-0.145	53	-0.329	-0.343	0.013
24.	-1.786	-1.859	-0.072	54	-0.453	-0.618	0.165
25.	-1.917	-1.730	0.187	55	-0.431	-0.514	0.083
26.	-1.883	-1.730	0.154	56	-0.229	-0.514	0.285
27.	-1.900	-1.730	0.170	57	-0.285	-0.354	0.069
28.	-1.950	-1.683	0.267	58	-0.163	-0.264	0.101
29.	-1.786	-1.475	0.312	59	-0.074	-0.096	0.022
30.	-1.835	-1.592	0.243	60	0.583	0.528	0.055

(-0.084), item 21 (-0.112), item 23 (-0.145), item 24 (-0.072), item 36 (-0.142), item 37 (-0.243), item 38 (-0.034), item 40 (-0.005), and item 50 (-0.179)

V. Research question five

What is the differential item functioning by school location using item local independence of both WAEC and NECO tests?

To determine the influence school location on the responses of WAEC multiple choice items, a Differential Item Functioning (DIF) was conducted on the data set using BILOG-MG3 item analysis computer programme to ascertain whether students who attended schools in the urban area were superior in their abilities as compared to their counterparts in the rural areas. Table 13 revealed the results of the differences based on the school location the students attended. The result shows that there was a major disparity in the ability of testees who attended schools in urban settings from their colleagues in the rural areas, as students in the urban schools had superior abilities in 27 out of the 50 items while those in rural schools had superior ability on just 16 items. The ability variances on the 33 items of the students in urban schools from their colleagues in rural schools includes item 1 (.057), item 3 (.071), item 5 (.057), item 7 (.027), item 11 (.026), item 21 (.111), item 23 (.122), item 25 (.126), item 27 (.065), item 29 (.103), item 30 (.020), item 31 (.042), item 32 (.024), item 33 (.082), item 35 (.180), item 36 (.040), item 37 (.106), item 38 (.068),

item 39 (.069), item 41 (.011), item 42 (.040), item 43 (.073), item 44 (.026), item 45 (.031), item 46 (.018), item 47 (.090), and item 48 (.126)

These numbers accounted for 54 % of the variance in the abilities of students who attended schools in the urban areas while the abilities of the testees who attended

TABLE 13

Differential Item Functioning (DIF) on the 2018 West African Examination Council (WAEC) multiple-choice item responses based on student's location

Items	Threshold			Items	Threshold		
	Urban	Rural	Difference		Urban	Rural	Difference
1.	-0.878	-0.820	0.057	31	-1.030	-0.988	0.042
2.	-0.865	-1.017	-0.152	32	-1.040	-1.016	0.024
3.	-1.001	-0.930	0.071	33	-1.020	-0.939	0.082
4.	-0.904	-1.002	-0.098	34	-1.015	-1.031	-0.015
5.	-1.040	-0.984	0.057	35	-1.071	-0.891	0.180
6.	-0.950	-1.061	-0.111	36	-1.006	-1.046	0.040
7.	-1.098	-1.071	0.027	37	-1.006	-0.900	0.106
8.	-0.972	-1.091	-0.119	38	-0.949	-1.017	0.068
9.	-1.103	-1.103	0.000	39	-0.982	-0.913	0.069
10.	-1.001	-1.113	-0.112	40	-0.979	-0.979	0.000
11.	-1.082	-1.056	0.026	41	-0.958	-0.948	0.011
12.	-1.051	-1.135	-0.084	42	-0.958	-0.998	0.040
13.	-1.087	-1.097	-0.010	43	-0.926	-0.853	0.073
14.	-1.040	-1.091	-0.051	44	-0.963	-0.988	0.026
15.	-1.098	-1.098	-0.000	45	-0.847	-0.816	0.031
16.	-1.030	-1.071	-0.040	46	-0.895	-0.913	0.018
17.	-1.093	-1.093	0.000	47	-0.830	-0.740	0.090
18.	-1.035	-1.066	-0.030	48	-0.813	-0.939	0.126
19.	-1.061	-1.061	0.000	49	-0.775	-0.775	0.000
20.	-1.046	-1.102	-0.056	50	-0.816	-0.816	0.000
21.	-1.077	-0.965	0.111				
22.	-1.030	-1.124	-0.093				
23.	-1.114	-0.993	0.122				
24.	-1.035	-1.124	-0.088				
25.	-1.143	-1.016	0.126				
26.	-1.015	-1.113	-0.097				
27.	-1.082	-1.016	0.065				
28.	-1.046	-1.071	-0.025				
29.	-1.082	-0.979	0.103				
30.	-1.050	-1.031	0.020				

schools in the rural areas accounted for only 32%. However, there was no disparity in the ability of testees who attended urban schools and rural school on item 9, 15, 17 19, 40, 49 and 50, which accounted for 14% of the total items.

Correspondingly, the ability variances on the 17 items of the students in urban schools from their colleagues in rural schools includes item 2 (.152), item 4 (.098), item 6 (.111), item 8 (.119), item 10 (.112), item 12 (.084), item 13 (.010), item 14 (.051), item 16 (.040), item 18 (.030), item 20 (.056), item 22 (.093), item 24 (.088), item 26 (.097), item 28 (.025) and item 34 (.015)

To determine the influence school location on the responses of NECO multiple choice items, a Differential Item Functioning (DIF) was conducted on the data set via BILOG-MG3 item analysis computer programme to ascertain whether students who attended schools in the urban area were superior in their abilities as compared to their equivalents in the rural areas. Table 14 showed the results of the differences based on the school location the testees attended. The result indicated that there was also a major difference in the ability of students who attended schools in urban settings from their colleagues in the rural areas, as students in the urban schools had superior abilities in 33 out of the 60 items while those in rural schools had superior ability on just 18 items.

The ability variances on the 33 items of the students in urban schools from their colleagues in rural schools includes item 1 (0.040), item 4 (0.000), item 5 (0.053), item 9 (0.036), item 10 (0.036), item 13 (0.157), item 14 (0.087), item 15 (0.318), item 16 (0.167), item 18 (0.135), item 20 (0.056), item 24 (0.039), item 25 (0.265), item 26 (0.104), item 27 (0.409), item 29 (0.207), item 30 (0.072), item 31 (0.103), item 34 (0.292), item 42 (0.149), item 43 (0.269), item 44 (0.073), item 45 (0.129), item 46 (0.201), item 47 (0.252), item 48 (0.204), item 50 (0.531), item 51 (0.175), item 52 (0.071), item 53 (0.272), item 55 (0.234), item 56 (0.049), item 57 (0.237), item 58 (0.111), item 59 (0.272) and item 60 (0.228)

These numbers accounted for 55 % of the variance in the abilities of students who attended schools in the urban areas while the abilities of the students who attended schools in the rural areas accounted for only 30%. However, there was no difference in the ability of students who attended urban schools and those from their counterparts in the rural areas on item 4, 7, 12 19, 28, 32, 41 and 59, which accounted for 15% of the total items.

Correspondingly, the ability variances on the 18 items of the students in urban schools from their colleagues in rural schools includes item 2 (0.040), item 6 (0.054), item 8 (0.035), item 11 (0.274), item 17 (0.100), item 21 (0.225), item 22 (0.061), item 23 (0.097), item 33 (0.239), item 35 (0.245), item 36 (0.276), item 37 (-0.163), item 38 (-0.282), item 39 (0.137), and item 40 (-0.201)

vi. Research question six:

What is the differential item functioning by school type using item local independence of both tests?

To determine the influence on the school type on the responses of WAEC multiple choice items, a Differential Item Functioning (DIF) was conducted on the data set via BILOG-MG3 item analysis computer programme to ascertain whether students who attended private schools were superior in their abilities as compared to their equals in the public schools. Table 15 showed the results of the differences based on the type of school the testees attended. The result indicated that there was a major difference in the

TABLE 14

Differential Item Functioning (DIF) on the 2018 National Examination Council (NECO) multiple-choice item responses based on student's location

Items	Threshold			Items	Threshold		
	Urban	Rural	Difference		Urban	Rural	Difference
1.	-1.792	-1.752	0.040	31	-1.746	-1.643	0.103
2.	-1.730	-2.057	-0.326	32	-1.174	-1.174	0.000
3.	-1.808	-1.968	-0.160	33	-1.611	-1.849	-0.239
4.	-1.856	-1.856	0.000	34	-1.904	-1.612	0.292
5.	-2.021	-2.075	0.053	35	-1.655	-1.899	-0.245
6.	-1.730	-1.784	-0.054	36	-1.524	-1.800	-0.276
7.	-2.074	-2.074	0.000	37	-1.670	-1.833	-0.163
8.	-2.021	-2.057	-0.035	38	-1.454	-1.736	-0.282
9.	-2.039	-2.003	0.036	39	-1.746	-1.883	-0.137
10.	-2.004	-1.968	0.036	40	-1.567	-1.768	-0.201
11.	-1.625	-1.900	-0.274	41	-1.553	-1.553	0.000
12.	-1.784	-1.784	0.000	42	-1.524	-1.674	0.149
13.	-1.496	-1.338	0.157	43	-1.553	-1.284	0.269
14.	-1.792	-1.705	0.087	44	-1.538	-1.465	0.073
15.	-2.039	-1.720	0.318	45	-1.454	-1.325	0.129
16.	-1.888	-1.720	0.167	46	-1.567	-1.366	0.201
17.	-1.700	-1.800	-0.100	47	-1.482	-1.230	0.252
18.	-1.855	-1.720	0.135	48	-1.655	-1.451	0.204
19.	-1.720	-1.720	0.000	49	-1.305	-1.305	0.000
20.	-1.761	-1.705	0.056	50	-1.655	-1.124	0.531
21.	-0.611	-0.836	-0.225	51	-0.509	-0.334	0.175
22.	-1.855	-1.916	-0.061	52	-0.588	-0.517	0.071
23.	-1.655	-1.752	-0.097	53	-0.211	-0.482	0.272
24.	-1.840	-1.800	0.039	54	-0.565	-0.565	0.000
25.	-1.954	-1.689	0.265	55	-0.364	-0.598	0.234
26.	-1.855	-1.752	0.104	56	-0.353	-0.402	0.049

27.	-2.021	-1.612	0.409	57	-0.211	-0.448	0.237
28.	-1.816	-1.816	0.000	58	-0.167	-0.278	0.111
29.	-1.730	-1.523	0.207	59	0.039	-0.233	0.272
30.	-1.746	-1.674	0.072	60	0.655	0.427	0.228

ability of students who attended private schools from their colleagues in the public schools, as they had superior abilities in 38 out of the 50 items while those in public school had superior ability on just 12 items. The ability variances on the 38 items of the students in private schools from their colleagues in public schools includes item 1 (.058), item 2 (.008), item 3 (.024), item 4 (.016), item 6 (.012), item 7 (.036), item 8 (.033), item 10 (.012), item 13 (.042), item 16 (.007), item 19 (.022), item 20 (.025), item 22 (.030), item 23 (.017), item 24 (.015), item 25 (.090), item 26 (.007), item 27 (.079), item 31 (.039), item 32 (.018), item 33 (.072), item 34 (.020), item 35 (.003), item 36 (.052), item 37 (.040), item 38 (.045), item 39 (.004), item 40 (.050), item 41 (.010), item 42 (.046), item 43 (.018), item 44 (.086), item 45 (.005), item 46 (.071), item 47 (.013), item 48 (.077), item 49 (.031) and item 50 (.028). These numbers accounted for 76 % of the variance in the abilities of testees who attended private schools while the abilities of the students in the public schools accounted for only 24%.

Correspondingly, the ability variances on the 12 items of the students in public schools from their colleagues in private schools includes item 5 (.030), item 9 (.033), item 11 (.033), item 12 (.022), item 14 (.038), item 15 (.059), item 17 (.011), item 18 (.007), item 21 (.055), item 28 (.042), item 29 (.009) and item 30 (.063)

In another development, in determining the influence school types on the responses of NECO multiple choice items, a Differential Item Functioning (DIF) was conducted on the data set using BILOG-MG3 item analysis computer programme to ascertain whether students who attended private schools were superior in their abilities as compared to their equivalents in the public schools. Table 16 showed the results of the differences based on the type of school the testees attended. The result shows that there

TABLE 15

Differential Item Functioning (DIF) on the 2018 West African Examination Council (WAEC) multiple-choice item responses based on school type

Items	Threshold Private	Threshold Public	Threshold Difference	Items	Threshold private	Threshold Public	Threshold Difference
1.	-0.812	-0.755	0.058	31	-0.957	-0.918	0.039
2.	-0.876	-0.868	0.008	32	-0.967	-0.948	0.018
3.	-0.909	-0.884	0.024	33	-0.944	-0.872	0.072
4.	-0.893	-0.877	0.016	34	-0.962	-0.942	0.020
5.	-0.927	-0.957	-0.030	35	-0.905	-0.909	0.003
6.	-0.940	-0.928	0.012	36	-0.980	-0.928	0.052
7.	-1.030	-0.994	0.036	37	-0.864	-0.904	0.040
8.	-0.975	-0.942	0.033	38	-0.935	-0.890	0.045
9.	-1.013	-1.046	-0.033	39	-0.880	-0.876	0.004
10.	-0.989	-0.977	0.012	40	-0.935	-0.885	0.050
11.	-0.980	-1.014	-0.033	41	-0.880	-0.890	0.010
12.	-1.008	-1.030	-0.022	42	-0.931	-0.885	0.046
13.	-1.041	-0.999	0.042	43	-0.832	-0.814	0.018
14.	-0.975	-1.013	-0.038	44	-0.949	-0.863	0.086
15.	-0.999	-1.058	-0.059	45	-0.766	-0.771	0.005
16.	-0.982	-0.975	0.007	46	-0.872	-0.801	0.071
17.	-1.013	-1.024	-0.011	47	-0.716	-0.729	0.013
18.	-0.975	-0.982	-0.007	48	-0.848	-0.771	0.077
19.	-0.998	-0.975	0.022	49	-0.727	-0.696	0.031
20.	-1.013	-0.987	0.025	50	-0.766	-0.738	0.028
21.	-0.922	-0.977	-0.055				
22.	-1.018	-0.987	0.030				
23.	-0.987	-0.971	0.017				

24.	-1.014	-0.999	0.015
25.	-1.052	-0.962	0.090
26.	-0.994	-0.987	0.007
27.	-1.019	-0.940	0.079
28.	-0.966	-1.008	-0.042
29.	-0.953	-0.962	-0.009
30.	-0.940	-1.003	-0.063

was also a major difference in the ability of students who attended private schools from their colleagues in the public schools, as they had superior abilities in 44 out of the 60 items while those in public school had superior ability on just 16 items. The ability variances on the 44 items of the students in private schools from their colleagues in public schools includes item 1 (.094), item 2 (.096), item 3 (.326), item 4 (.031), item 5 (.116), item 6 (.157), item 7 (.010), item 8 (.098), item 11 (.313), item 14 (.328), item 16 (.190), item 18 (.253), item 22 (.030), item 23 (.079), item 24 (.095), item 26 (.063), item 27 (.206), item 28 (.143), item 29 (.227), item 30 (.155), item 33 (.063), item 34 (.188), item 35 (.126), item 38 (.005), item 41 (.287), item 42 (.010), item 43 (.185), item 44 (.035), item 45 (.127), item 46 (.203), item 47 (.193), item 48 (.386), item 49 (.228), item 50 (.361), item 51 (.126), item 52 (.279), item 53 (.011), item 54 (.347), item 55 (.075), item 56 (.325), item 57 (.133), item 58 (.141), item 59 (.148), and item 60 (.013). These numbers accounted for 73.3 % of the variance in the abilities of students who attended private schools while the abilities of the testees in the public schools accounted for only 26.7%.

In the same way, the ability variances on the 16 items of the students in public schools from their colleagues in private schools includes item 9 (.028), item 10 (.177), item

12 (.110), item 13 (.046), item 15 (.084), item 17 (.110), item 19 (.044), item 20 (.110), item 21 (.092), item 25 (.127), item 31 (.028), item 32 (.011), item 36 (.072), item 37 (.077), item 39 (.080) and item 40 (.057).

TABLE 16

Differential Item Functioning (DIF) on the 2018 National Examination Council (NECO) multiple-choice item responses based on school type

Items	Threshold			Items	Threshold		
	Private	public	Difference		Private	Public	Difference
1.	-1.825	-1.731	0.094	31	-1.687	-1.715	-0.028
2.	-1.938	-1.842	0.096	32	-1.168	-1.178	-0.011
3.	-2.057	-1.731	0.326	33	-1.763	-1.700	0.063
4.	-1.873	-1.842	0.031	34	-1.857	-1.669	0.188
5.	-2.109	-1.994	0.116	35	-1.841	-1.715	0.126
6.	-1.841	-1.685	0.157	36	-1.628	-1.700	-0.072
7.	-2.074	-2.064	0.010	37	-1.717	-1.794	-0.077
8.	-2.092	-1.994	0.098	38	-1.599	-1.594	0.005
9.	-2.011	-2.039	-0.028	39	-1.778	-1.859	-0.080
10.	-1.905	-2.082	-0.177	40	-1.643	-1.700	-0.057
11.	-1.922	-1.609	0.313	41	-1.444	-1.731	0.287
12.	-1.731	-1.841	-0.110	42	-1.599	-1.609	0.010
13.	-1.403	-1.449	-0.046	43	-1.336	-1.521	0.185
14.	-1.922	-1.594	0.328	44	-1.527	-1.492	0.035
15.	-1.841	-1.925	-0.084	45	-1.336	-1.463	0.127
16.	-1.905	-1.715	0.190	46	-1.376	-1.579	0.203
17.	-1.700	-1.810	-0.110	47	-1.270	-1.463	0.193
18.	-1.922	-1.669	0.253	48	-1.376	-1.762	0.386
19.	-1.702	-1.747	-0.044	49	-1.193	-1.421	0.228
20.	-1.684	-1.794	-0.110	50	-1.218	-1.579	0.361
21.	-0.689	-0.781	-0.092	51	-0.376	-0.501	0.126
22.	-1.905	-1.875	0.030	52	-0.431	-0.710	0.279
23.	-1.748	-1.669	0.079	53	-0.365	-0.354	0.011

24.	-1.873	-1.778	0.095	54	-0.387	-0.733	0.347
25.	-1.762	-1.889	-0.127	55	-0.531	-0.456	0.075
26.	-1.841	-1.778	0.063	56	-0.234	-0.559	0.325
27.	-1.922	-1.715	0.206	57	-0.409	-0.276	0.133
28.	-1.889	-1.747	0.143	58	-0.169	-0.310	0.141
29.	-1.748	-1.521	0.227	59	-0.039	-0.187	0.148
30.	-1.794	-1.639	0.155	60	0.527	0.514	0.013

4.3 Discussion of findings

This segment is dedicated to the discussion of findings of the research questions.

The discussion was made in accordance to each research questions.

4.3.1 Dimensionality of objective test items.

The research question assessing the dimensionality of sets of 2018 WAEC and NECO mathematics objective test items revealed that the examinations were not unidimensional but multidimensional. The result corroborates Ubi, Joshua and Umoinyang (2012) that examinations designed for selection of testees might not be solely unidimensional particularly when items are developed from a broad syllabus. Stressing that mathematics objective test items are developed on the contents which range from chemistry, physics, biology and even agricultural concepts as reflected in the measurement objectives for the syllabus. The result is also in tandem with Kamat (2005) that science related subjects/courses contribute to the items in measuring multiple dimensions and not only one dimension. It is difficult to situate a sole factor when assessing a wide ability or characteristic, especially when the measure contains numerous items with diverse levels

of accuracy. A lone factor can be achieved only when items on an instrument are homogenous which implies that items assess related content with small number of items, center on barely defined content, and have the equivalent level of accuracy. Items developed in education, psychology, sciences and or social sciences habitually measured broad constructs that cover diverse aspects of attribute manifestation which supported the multidimensionality of the result.

4.3.2 Local independence of objective test item

The research question assessing local independence of 2018 WAEC and NECO mathematics objective test items revealed that there was significant evidence of local independence in the WAEC and NECO items as the tetrachoric correlation coefficients of the items were significantly very low. This result implies that most of the items were not related and may not act as hints to responding to other items. This result agrees with Akpan (1989) that the ability which influences responses to any two items in a test is constant, thus the association between the two items should not be at variance from zero; stressing that if it does, then the answers to the items are affected by factors different from the ones the test instrument was designed to assess. On such factors, the test takers who have the same ability level but different response pattern reveal nonexistence of local independence among or between the items making the test. This result is also in tandem with Ubi (2006) that once the responses of test takers on some test items has been determined to a greater extent, then, there will be no additional factors that consistently influence such responses;

stressing that in a set of mathematics test items for instance, the response a test taker provides to item number one should not be influenced by the response given to item number two, and so on.

4.3.3 Model fit of objective test item

The research question assessing model fit of 2018 WAEC and NECO mathematics objective test items revealed that 10 WAEC items representing 20% of the test and 19 NECO items representing 31.7% respectively were indicative of bad items because the items did not fit some IRT logistic models. This result agrees with Lee (2004) that if objective test items is not modeled to any of the parameters, the discrimination parameters of the mutually dependent items will be undervalued, stressing that the discrimination parameter and guessing parameter depend on the difficulty of the item it intermingle with, but not on the difficulty of the item itself. Due to the effect the difficulty parameter on the discrimination parameter, the negative local independence shrinks the item information and the standard error of measurement is underestimated. No single model-data fit index detects all of the possible sources of fit or misfit. The result is also in tandem with Balazs and De Boeck (2006) that ignoring Local Item Dependence can have grave penalty for the goodness of fit of a model, for the parameter estimates and for confidence intervals, stressing that if trait level is not restricted, local independence signifies that no association remains between the items.

4.3.4 Differential item function (Gender) and local independence

The research question assessing the influence of gender on item local independence of sets of 2018 WAEC and NECO mathematics objective test items revealed that there is no significant variation on the ability of both group of students in mathematics. This result

agrees with Banbow and Stanley (2010) that if the males and females had presumably fundamentally the same amount of training in mathematics it apparent that differential course-taking in mathematics cannot alone explain the sex difference in mathematics ability. They stressed that gender-based effects have minimal influence on the item responses. Differences in interest in mathematics and other science oriented courses between sexes are not responsible for respond variations in the subject. Inconsistent responses to test items in science are not influenced by biological factors rather cultural or social factors such as feelings towards science, type of schooling, and the socialization process, as well as cultural and institutional factors as being accountable for gender disparity in item responses of science courses.

This result negates Tennen (2005) that when test takers run into mathematics difficulties, males are likely to credit difficulties to challenges inherent in the subjects using their abilities, while the females are more likely to explain response inconsistencies with lack of ability, stressing that regarding general academic performance, females are more likely to ascribe inconsistent response in mathematics to lack of ability, while males often attribute it to lack of hard work or unfamiliar treatment. Differences in the Mathematics responses among test takers are due to many factors, such as causal attribution, environmental factors and teacher related factors are not their abilities.

4.3.5 Differential item function (School location) and local independence

The research question assessing the influence of school location on item local independence of sets of 2018 WAEC and NECO mathematics objective test items revealed that there is a important disparity on the ability of students whose schools are located in the urban areas from the students whose schools are situated in the rural areas, as students in urban schools showed superior abilities in responding to the test items that those in rural

schools This result agrees with Suzanne and Lauren (2012) that rural schools do not always have access to the equivalent level of federal funding as urban and suburban schools and this can hinder the opportunity testees have for learning mathematics which is evidence in the violation of local independence, stressing that students in urban areas demonstrate improved and consistence responses to test items than their rural equals in mathematics, reading, and sciences. Rural schools encounter challenges that lead to adverse educational outcomes for their students. One of such challenges is lack of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) usage, which is usually deficient in rural areas, as these challenges could ultimately lead to violation in item consistency.

This result is also in tandem with Caplan and Lawrence (2014) that the availability of less facilities in several rural schools than those in urban areas have been found to contribute to a more inadequate curricula being made available at these rural schools. Stressing that since the curricula could not be implemented fully by the teachers in terms of content coverage it will invariably affect student's response pattern which is a violation in the local independence of the test items. The urban-rural difference in the response patterns of the students is responsible for factors such as an uneven distribution of resources and lack of functional facilities. The violation of item local independence as well as the variation in student abilities could be attributed to factors such as qualified teachers who are not willing to take up teaching appointment as well as those already in the system are not willing to put in their best in rural schools for lack of motivation for teachers. Several rural communities also lack electricity, good transport system, communication System as well as several other infrastructural deficiencies which together retarded educational advancement in the rural areas.

Nevertheless this result is contrary to the finding of Hattie (2004) that when a learner has extreme likeness for an activity, object and event, he interacts with it more frequently; otherwise, he withdraws from it or has as little interaction with it as possible, stressing that interest in mathematics could be evident from the way a student is punctual in class, paying attention in class work, assignments and tests, as well as taking delight in observing and exploring the environment. This likes and dislikes to mathematics as a subject could lead to a major violation in local independence of test items and vice versa and not where the school is located. Interest not school location plays a crucial role in the teaching/learning process. At the classroom level and beyond, learning can be meaningfully achieved within the context of optimal disposition of the learner to the tasks in question. This means that the learner needs to be psychologically present and attentive towards the learning tasks. Situations often arise in which the learner may be physically present but psychologically absent in the classroom. Students that are interested in mathematics are likely to respond consistently to test items which is a non violation to local independence of the test items. This result also negates Momoh and Uka (2006) that rural students are privileged by little class size and benefit from more individual attention from teachers than their urban equals, noting that this individual attention could pave the way in terms of how they respond to test items.

4. 3.6. Differential item function by the type of school and local independence

The research question assessing the impact of school type on item local independence of sets of 2018 WAEC and NECO mathematics objective test items revealed that there is a important disparity on the ability of students who attended private schools and their counterparts in government schools, as students in private schools showed

superior abilities in responding to the test items than those in urban schools. This result conform Howell and Peterson (2002) that a large amount publicly owned schools are characterized by deteriorating structures, physical ramshackle building which could adversely hampers students' cognitive development. Non-motivated teachers especially in government schools will have a harmful effect on the students' academic performance as they may not be able to contend with their private equivalent. They stressed that students in public schools often come from economically poor and average income families. The families face a variety of tribulations causing emotional disorder among their kids which may result in response inconsistency of items. Private schools tend to have many more high socio-economic status students than the public schools where parents provide every learning aid which could ultimately lead to better academic performance and consistence response to test items which is in consonance with the assumption of local independence.

This result also agrees with Crosne and Elder (2004) that school ownership, provision of amenities and availability of facilities are school is an significant structural section of the school. Private schools due to the improved funding, small sizes, stern ownership, motivated faculty and access to facilities such as computers, are likely to inviolate local independence of the items than students from public schools. These added funding resources and amenities found in private schools boost student's academic ability, their response consistencies and generally increases their educational attainments. The level of school administrators' participation in decision making about the school matters is high in private secondary schools, instructors agreed in private schools have dedicated instructors, financial capacity, good and skilled school administrators, and dynamic inspectorate human resources. The researcher concluded that all the aforementioned

parameters could aid item local independence by students in private schools and verse versa.

This result negates Coleman and Hoffer (2011) that resolutions by parents or policymakers about private secondary school choice are often entrenched in the postulation that, by choosing private secondary schools, families will progress the academic groundwork of their kids. Stressing that once testee background qualities are taken into account, the disparity in their true abilities between public and private school testees practically disappear. In effect, these researchers noted that, the variation in ability may have small to do with how a school is funded and governed; rather, it may perhaps be an object of other variables, together with testee's socioeconomic status, parental education, community support, or peer group character.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter is dedicated with the summary and conclusion of the complete research work. The chapter is consequently presented under the subsequent sub-headings:

5.1 Summary of the study

5.2 Conclusion

5.3 Recommendations

5.4 Suggestions for further studies

5.1 Summary of the study

The rationale of this study was to assess dimensionality and local independence of 2018 West African Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) mathematics objective test items. To accomplish the purpose of this study, the subsequent five research questions were posted to guide the study.

1. Which are the dimensions of 2018 WAEC and NECO Mathematics objective test items?
2. What are the local independence of 2018 WAEC and NECO Mathematics objective test items?

3. Which are the items of 2018 WAEC and NECO Mathematics objective test items that fit the one-parameter, two-parameter and three parameter logistic models?
4. What is the differential item functioning by gender using item local independence of both tests?
5. What is the differential item functioning by location using item local independence of both tests?
6. What is the differential item functioning by school type using item local independence of both tests?

Literature review was carryout according to the variables under study. Descriptive research design was adopted for the study. It is a scientific method which entails observing and describing the actions of a subject without influencing it in any way. The main purpose of this type of design is to accurately describe the features of a sample and to generalize the result to the entire population. This design is applied because it's entails partial coverage of the population under investigation and the sample is taken at random. A sample of 1014 respondents was chosen from the study area. Stratified sampling method was employed to choose the sample for the study. The 2018 West African Examination Council (WAEC) and the National Examination Council (NECO) mathematics objective tests were the instruments adopted and used for data collection.

The instrument was regarded valid in all respect, as the two examination bodies are known for standardization in item construction. The instruments were however, presented to the supervisors and specialists in measurement and evaluation in the department of Educational foundations, Faculty of Education, University of Calabar, Calabar, for face and content validation. The reliability coefficient estimates of the instruments were

established through Kuder Richardson (K-R 20) reliability method to check its internal consistency. Confirmatory Factor analysis, chi-square values of 1-parameter, 2-parameter and 3-parameter Logistic Item Response Theory (IRT) models, and Differential Item Functioning (DIF), using Bilog-MG3 statistical computer software were the statistical analysis procedures employed to answer the research questions under the study.

The results of the research questions on WAEC bothering on dimensionality reveal that twelve (12) factors had eigenvalues over the kaiser's criterion of 1 and in combination explained 19.26%. Thus, the first eigenvalue was 9.631 larger than the next eleven eigenvalues (7.738, 3.745, 2.758, 2.705, 2.600, 2.170, 1.770, 1.525, 1.476, 1.269 and 1.046) respectively. The first factor explained only 19.26% of the variance in the data set. The second factor variance explained 15.48% of the left over variance. The rest of the variance was explained by the other 48 factors with 10 factors each having a percentage of variance between 7.50 and 2.50, then 38 factors each having a proportion of variance of between 2.10 and .08. The last 38 factors were removed because they did not add to a simple factor structure and failed to meet a least standard of having a major factor loading of greater than 1 eigenvalues. The WAEC and NECO result bothering on the dimensionality revealed that the two examinations were not unidimensional but multidimensional. The WAEC result on the chi-square goodness of fit analysis revealed that 40 items representing 80% of the WAEC test were considered good items and the remaining 10 items representing 20% of the test were indicative of bad items and were required to be dropped from the test or revised.

In a related development, the result bothering on the local independence of 2018 WAEC and NECO revealed that, to a large extent the items were significantly local

independence. Similarly, the WAEC (DIF) result revealed that male students had superior abilities than their female counterparts on 27 items while their female counterparts had superior abilities than their male counterparts on 22 items while there was no disparity in ability between the male and female testees on item 7. While the result of students on school location shows that there was a major difference in the ability of testees who attended schools in urban settings from their colleagues in the rural areas, as students in the urban schools had superior abilities in 27 out of the 50 items than their rural counterpart while those in rural schools had superior ability on just 16 items than their urban counterparts. Though, there was no variation in the ability of students who attended urban schools and rural schools on item 9, 15, 17, 19, 40, 49 and 50. In another development, the result on school type regarding students' ability revealed that there was a major variation in the ability of students who attended private schools from their colleagues in the public schools, as they had superior abilities in 38 out of the 50 items while those in public school had superior ability on just 12 items.

In another development, the results of the research questions on NECO bothering on dimensionality reveals that sixteen (16) factors had eigenvalues over the kaiser's criterion of 1 and in combination explained 14.33%. Thus, the first eigenvalue was 8.597 superior than the next fifteen eigenvalues (7.491, 3.964, 3.739, 2.761, 2.547, 2.440, 1.937, 1.873, 1.675, 1.518, 1.451, 1.365, 1.279, 1.221 and 1.144) respectively. The first factor explained only 14.33% of the variance in the data set. The second factor variance explained 12.49% of the remaining variance. The rest of the variance was explained by the other 58 factors with 14 factors each having a percentage of variance between 6.61 and 1.91, then 44 factors each containing a proportion of variance of between 1.70 and .044. The last 44 factors were

removed since they did not add to a simple factor structure and failed to meet a least criteria of containing a most important factor loading of superior than 1 eigenvalues.

Also, the NECO result on the chi-square goodness of fit analysis revealed that 41 items representing 68.3% of the NECO test were considered good items and the remaining 19 items representing 31.7% of the test were indicative of bad items and were necessary to be dropped from the test or revised. Moreover, the NECO DIF result revealed that male students had superior abilities on 43 items while their female counterparts had superior abilities on only 17 item items; the NECO result on school location revealed that there was also a major distinction in the ability of students who attended schools in urban settings from their colleagues in the rural areas, as students in the urban schools had superior abilities in 33 out of the 60 items while those in rural schools had superior ability on just 18 items. However, there was no difference in the ability of students who attended urban schools and those from their counterparts in the rural areas on item 4, 7, 12 19, 28, 32, 41and 59; while the result on the abilities of students regarding the type of school revealed also that there was also a major difference in the ability of students who attended private schools from their colleagues in the public schools, as they had superior abilities in 44 out of the 60 items while those in public school had superior ability on just 16 items.

Based on the result of the study, it was recommended that: Examination bodies in the country should commit itself to the development of items that fit objective test and modern assessment models like the Racsh, 2- and 3-parameter models which could lead to reduction in unfair and bias measurement of students' abilities. Management of schools should provide modern assessment software, train and encourage test experts in the development of quality items for estimation of true students' abilities. Assessment of

students' abilities in a test using the global score should gradually give way to the use of contemporary assessment techniques like the Item Response Theory (IRT), as this method provides detailed and multipurpose options in evaluating the exact proficiencies in students. The government should make the teaching and learning environment conducive for all teachers both in urban and rural schools in order for them to give their best in curriculum implementation. And adequate learning facilities in school should be provided especially in rural and government owned schools to boost learning especially on the part of the learners.

3.2 Conclusion

Based on the result and findings of the study, the subsequent conclusions were arrived at: Through the dimensional analysis of both tests (WEAC and NECO), it was discovered that the Mathematics examination multiple choice instruments were not unidimensional. This implies that during the ability-by- task interaction during the test taking by the test examinees, there were some demands by some items that stimulated trait other than their true ability under what was measured. This accounted for the multidimensionality of the test.

The WAEC and NECO items were to a large extent locally independent

While attempt by the two examination bodies in developing quality items for public examinations is cherished, most of the items were not fit for the objective test and suitable assessment of what the examinations were projected to assess, as some items did not fit the IRT models. Moreover, the result also submitted that students' ability in responding to any science-oriented course/subject is not influenced by gender. That is, the male students do not possess superior ability to their female counterparts in mathematics achievement test.

Students in urban schools do better in science-oriented subject/courses in terms of ability than their colleagues in rural areas, while students in private schools have significant superior abilities than their counterparts in public schools

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the conclusion of the study, the subsequent recommendations are made:

Examination bodies in the country should commit themselves to the development of items that fit objective test and contemporary assessment models like the Rasch, 2- and 3-parameter models which could lead to reduction in unfair and bias measurement of students' abilities. Management of schools should provide modern assessment software, train and encourage test experts in the development of quality items for estimation of true students' abilities.

Assessment of students' abilities in a test using the global score should gradually give way to the use of modern assessment techniques like the Item Response Theory (IRT), as this method provides detailed and multipurpose options in evaluating the exact proficiencies in students.

The government should make the teaching and learning environment conducive for all teachers both in urban and rural schools in order for them to give their best in curriculum implementation. Adequate learning facilities in school should be provided especially in rural and government owned schools to boost learning.

5.4 Suggestions for further studies

Based on the discovery of the study, the subsequent proposition were made for further studies:

A reproduction of the research should be carried out to assess the examination carried out by Ministry of Education in Cross River State so as to determine the legitimacy of the current findings.

Concerned scholars should carry out comparative research on the use of Classical test theory and Item Response theory on students' proficiency in mathematics multiple choice examination in Cross River State

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